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REPORT ON TRADE-OFFS AND CO-BENEFITS

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Table of content

1. Glossary	5
1.1. Abbreviations	6
2. Introduction	7
2.1. How to use this report?	7
3. Methodology	7
3.1 Mapping	7
3.2 Interviews	8
3.3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	9
4. Discussion of results	10
4.1 Visions of Safe & Sustainable Food Systems	10
4.2 Definitions of Sustainability in Food Systems	11
4.3 Indicators for Sustainability	12
4.4 Governance Structures	13
4.5 Methodologies for Change	14
4.6 Needs and Gaps	15
5. Recommendations	16
5.1 Relevance of this report for the development of the hub of food system labs	16
5.2 Relevance for this report for the development of the SRIA, RIPE and policy advice	16
5.3 Relevance for further work in WP7	17
5.4 Relevance for development of the Prototype Partnership	17
6. Annexes	19
6.1 Blank mapping template	20
6.2 Mapped Cases WP7	23
6.3 Interview Guide	79
6.4 Interviews	86
	0

1. Glossary

- **Farm to Fork Strategy:** The Farm to Fork Strategy is part of the European Green Deal and it aims to accelerate our transition to a sustainable food system (website).
- **Governance:** The process, or the power, of governing; the specific system by which the Partnership is ruled,
- **Hub:** A physical or virtual space providing opportunities for knowledge sharing, networking, and exchange
- **Mirror Groups:** A group of individuals who provide input, feedback, reflections, and recommendations on an organisation/work being done. Working with mirror groups provides FOODPathS with an opportunity to learn about best governance and implementation practices and elevate the participants' voices and stories, including their priorities, reflections, and feedback, to ensure an inclusive, transparent partnership.
- **Participatory Processes:** refers to the active involvement of the people or the community in policy-formulation, project- planning or implementation (website).
- **Partnership:** an arrangement where parties agree to cooperate to advance their mutual interests,
- **Prototype:** An original form, or model (described in detail) which is the basis for the future Partnership,
- **Social inclusion:** Social inclusion is the process of improving the terms on which individuals and groups take part in society, improving the ability, opportunity, and dignity of those disadvantaged on the basis of their identity (website).
- **Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems:** a sustainable food system provides and promotes safe, nutritious and healthy food of low environmental impact for all current and future EU citizens in a manner that itself also protects and restores the natural environment and its ecosystem services, is robust and resilient, economically dynamic, just and fair, and socially acceptable and inclusive (website).
- **Sustainable Food System Deals:** for the purpose of this paper safe and sustainable food system deals are initiatives, networks, partnerships, policy frameworks, and programs that have an overarching aim to transform the food system from a linear, extractive model, towards a circular and sustainable one. 'Deals' include more than one stakeholder and raise questions regarding benefits and trade-offs.
- **Systemic or Systems approach:** Within and affecting a whole system, with interacting actors and feedback loops.
- **Vulnerable groups:** Groups within our societies that face higher risk of poverty and social exclusion compared to the general population. These vulnerable and marginalised groups include but are not limited to: people with disabilities, migrants and ethnic minorities (including Roma), homeless people, ex-prisoners, drug addicts, people with alcohol problems, isolated older people and children (website).

1.1. Abbreviations

CAP= Common Agricultural Policy

FS = Food Systems;

KPI = Key Performance Indicators;

RIPE = Research & Innovation & Science to Policy & Education;

SRIA = Strategic Research & innovation agenda;

SFS = Sustainable Food System(s)

2. Introduction

Through this report we present our findings regarding mechanisms and characteristics of inclusive sustainable food system 'deals.' These deals range from public-private partnerships to global civil engagement programs to bottom-up stakeholder initiatives. The focus of this report is on 1) the identification of critical issues related to un-safe and unsustainable food systems and 2) the identification of successful best practices for food system transformation including co-operations, voluntary agreements, and policies.

The contents in this report are the results of desk-research mapping of case studies and in-depth interviews that shed light into critical issues causing un-safe and unsustainable food systems, actions being taken to overcome these issues, existing networks, platforms, and partnerships, and sustainability indicators.

The first part of this report includes background information about the process and methodology related to how the information was gathered and the learnings derived. In the second part the findings of our activities are shared in a combined analysis and synthesis and finally with recommendations for the FoodPathS consortium and the future partnership on sustainable food systems based on our findings.

2.1. How to use this report?

This report is written for the FoodPathS consortium members and the future partners of the Sustainable Food System Partnership. FoodPathS consortium members and future Partnership partners are especially encouraged to read the 'recommendations' section. When questions arise about the recommendations, readers can consult the 'Discussion of Results,' 'Methodology,' and 'Glossary' sections. This report was written to encourage inclusive and meaningful synergies between the future Partnership with organisations in- and outside Europe by learning from and cooperating with existing networks and partnerships.

The report shares learnings about and different perspectives on key opportunities, challenges, and priorities related to co-benefits and trade-offs of transformation towards sustainable food systems at local, national, EU-wide, and global scales. The intention is that consortium members and future Partnership partners will consider these learnings and perspectives in order to ensure the Partnership in a manner that is inclusive of different contexts, realities and views across scales, chains, actors and organisations.

3. Methodology

3.1 Mapping

Mapping in WP7 aims to understand the main characteristics of safe and sustainable food systems by identifying existing networks, platforms, and partnerships and their work to understand: 1) critical issues related to un-safe and unsustainable FS, and 2) successful best practices including co-operations, voluntary agreements, and policies to address them. Thus, the cases collected focus on addressing critical issues causing un-safe and unsustainable food systems. In this results section we look at examples of networks,

platforms, and partnership, challenges they address, action taken to overcome the challenges, and sustainability indicators.

We identified a range of existing networks, platforms and partnerships. Several cases mapped were directly related to networks focusing on food policies (Milan Food Policy, New York Food Policy, Berlin Food Council) and cases of collaboration between civil society and municipalities. Those networks of actors are very diverse and adaptable in terms of who participated e.g city staff, NGO personnel, farmers, citizens, business owners. The goal of those cooperations is mostly to influence policies or actions on food systems at local levels, taking into account the diversity of the local supply chains and their inherent boundaries. The cooperations react to the fact that a more inclusive and resilient food system relies on inclusive, fair and environmentally healthy food supply chains, meaning in all sectors of the food system, be it production, recycling or consumption in linear or circular food supply chains. Other partnerships occur at different points along the supply chain or along a circular supply chain and were facilitated by a third actor or ‘intervener.’ For example, the App “ResQ” is a case, where two parts of the supply chain – supermarkets and consumers – are part of a facilitated partnership. The MUFPP integrates circular elements into the supply chain such as food redistribution mechanisms and food waste handling. A third type are cases looked at networks and partnerships facilitated by platforms where one agency (public or private) takes the lead and drives for action, such as the “Ellen McArthur Foundation”, “4per1000” or the “One Planet Network Sustainable Food Systems Programme”.

Most cases mapped were funded by public or private agencies or had the support of donated/in-kind time and volunteer labor. The activities mapped include both top-down and bottom-up initiatives. The difference between a top-down or bottom-up actions lies, in most of the cases, in the presence or absence of policy makers and in the funding availability. The top-down activities received some degree of funding from public or private agencies and included policy interventions. The bottom-up activities were often local/regional, while top-down actions tend to be also international.

In addition, we noted that the better embedded practices, or else the practices that were more successful, are also the ones in which the network of actors is more diverse. Finally, from what we were able to observe in the mapping, the success of the cases mapped depended on having a funded coordinator.

3.2 Interviews

According to the description of task 7.2 and the purpose of WP7, we designed a questionnaire template for the interview. The goals of the interviews were prescribed as:

- To bilaterally engage and learn from existing initiatives (e.g. Policy & City Labs, social innovation trajectories) and global organisations (FAO, WFP, WHO, UNICEF, UN Nutrition, etc.), national and sub national governments
- To identify best governance and implementation practices
- To identify “SFS deals” at global, national and subnational level
- To identify potential mirror group participants
- Document lessons learned from best practices especially related to policy and governance

The interviewees were selected together with WP partners on the basis of the mapping of actors looking at the following categories: existing initiatives (e.g. Policy & City Labs, social innovation trajectories), global organisations (FAO, WFP, WHO, UNICEF, UN Nutrition, etc.) as well as national and sub national governments. After conducting a broad mapping of actors, we selected interviewees to have a balanced representation of “Scales of Action” (which scale they primarily influence local, regional, national, global), “Area of Focus” (which topic they interact with) and their geographical location. At this stage, we already foresaw the potential of interviewed actors to be prominent candidates for the Mirror Groups.

For the analysis of the interviews, we used a deductive approach and applied the questions asked to the participants as categories. These categories were: Identifies main challenges in food systems as ..., activities to overcome challenges related to sustainable food systems, expectations towards food system change, definition(s) of sustainability, dealing with disagreement/"rival" stakeholders. In a second step, we used an inductive approach to identify emerging main topics that came up throughout the interviews and were not yet included in the categories. We compared each question between the interviews in order to identify both the common themes and the unique points of each organization/initiative. For example, recurring methods on how to foster agreement (“shared vision”) or specificities e.g., due to the location of the organization.

3.3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Partners in WP7 initially planned to map 30 organisations and ‘deals’ and to interview 5-10 individuals and organisations each (for a total of between 20 to 40). In the end, 33 organisations were mapped as part of WP2, and 25 individuals and organisations were interviewed. The number of organisations mapped and interviewed was constrained by timeline and availability. However, this bilateral engagement of organisations outside the consortium will continue as part of other tasks in WP7 via conversations, workshops, and mirror groups.

For the mapping, our plan was to have a wide, but also qualitatively relevant selection. We therefore asked all WP partners to identify a first list of practices that were considered more relevant for them and that could help us to identify: A) critical issues causing un-safe and unsustainable FS, B) actions being taken to overcome these issues, C) existing networks, platforms, and partnerships, D) sustainability indicators. In turn, we reviewed the practices suggested and organize a meeting with WP partners filter the successful best practices and identify the criteria for defining SFS partnership at the local, national, EU, and global scales. This collaborative approach allowed us to learn more about the different practices, share knowledge across partners and strengthen our mapping activity.

For the interviews, we aimed for a balanced representation of organisations operating on different scales (global, EU, national and local) and focus areas (government, non-government, social interventions, approaches to sustainability e.g., farming, health, policy). However, of the 23 interviews 14 were global organisations, 5 EU, 4 National, and 3 were local organisations. While this does not meet the initially planned target, it does meet the ultimate goal of bringing in new voices into the process of developing a partnership and provides for opportunities to learn from and align with global organisations and initiatives focusing on under-represented voices such as the just food transition and women farmers. Furthermore, several

organisations work directly with local organisations and were able to share an aggregated perspective from their local partners and stakeholders, further helping to meet the targeted goal of balanced representation.

4. Discussion of results

While the mapping primarily focused on identifying needs and gaps, the results of the interviews are discussed below according to the following 6 themes. The needs and gaps from the mapping are included in the sections focusing on definitions of sustainability, indicators for sustainability and needs gaps and are discussed in those sections.

1. Vision of Safe and Sustainable Food Systems
2. Definitions of Sustainability
3. Indicators for Sustainability
4. Governance Structures
5. Methodologies for Change
6. Needs and Gaps

4.1 Visions of Safe & Sustainable Food Systems

Visions are very powerful. Quoting Elena Benett with visions of the future “it's like steering a car - you are going to steer towards what you are looking at”¹. Unsurprisingly the importance of shared visions for SFS have been a main take-away from the interviews. Unfortunately, at the moment food systems suffer from unaligned understandings and means for change - if we strive for a different system, aligned positions of how this should look like are vital. A shared vision is the basis for change as well as a motivator for stakeholders and with common goals compromises and trade-offs can be easier to accept since they act as means to an end. All stakeholders in food systems should be made aware of the importance of their opinion and be included in a visioning process.

Certain features of a shared vision of a SFS were mentioned frequently in the interviews. This may possibly be organized and supervised by a coordinating force that ensures equal access to opportunities and influence for all stakeholders. The distribution of power and responsibility seems to be a prominent feature. In an envisioned SFS risks, power and responsibility is shared equally along the whole system, supply chains as well as policy processes. Environmental, social, health and climate impacts are equally accounted for. No stakeholders responsibility is exaggerated (at the moment consumer's & producer's) or understated (at the moment private for-profit actors'). At the same time power imbalances have to be identified and representation in policy processes have to match the share of work and service a stakeholder group conducts in the food system; for example farmers have a crucial role in delivering environmental services while their representation on a European level is relatively small in comparison to e.g. commercial companies. In order for all actors to actively participate, education and training on food topics is fostered and made available to everyone. Funding and support schemes would have to distribute according to the level of change a sector

is facing: Meaning to acknowledge marginal and investment costs that smaller enterprises in the supply chain are facing through a system change.

The interviewees identify a future SFS that acknowledges the different levels of food systems in order to find adequate solutions, define trade-offs and benefits between those: There is a global food system that has to be governed by global solutions, inter-state regulations and law. But at the same time there are local food systems containing informal rules, habits and restrictions, such as food traditions, selling points for food, seasonal and regional specificities in species, behaviors and labor. Due to the interconnection of food systems there are trade-offs and co-benefits at and between all scales (local to local, global to local etc.). Since food systems are highly dependent on local contexts (weather, cultural aspects, dietary patterns) a future SFS acknowledges the voice of the local communities, including the marginalized groups, and aligns local policies to build strong, resilient and adaptable local food systems. This finding aligns with the results of the mapping, which showed that the most successful actions are those that guarantee the participation of a variety of actors. SFS must ensure high quality of life for all producers, processors, retailers, and consumers. Data and funds should be made available to local authorities and partnerships to build up efficient local supply chains and calculate their true costs and decide on necessary trade-offs. Local food policies and strategies should be rooted in legislation, as well as, take every form of knowledge into account, including traditional or indigenous knowledge.

The vision we are seeing emerge includes new policy frameworks and updating outdated/conflicting policies at the EU, national, and local levels, taking into account and building upon diverse knowledge and expertise from the whole supply chain.

4.2 Definitions of Sustainability in Food Systems

Sustainability is a term frequently used when talking about transformation towards carbon neutral agricultural practices and food supply chains that engage in regenerative or nature-positive methods. Once defined through the Brundtland commission sustainability means “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”² Still, when looking at food systems it can be a very broad term and depending on the context it can mean different things. In FAO’s 2014 definition, a sustainable food system ensures food security and nutrition for all in a such a way that the economic, social and environmental bases to generate food security and nutrition of future generations are not compromised¹. The Science Advice for Policy by European Academics (SAPEA) working group defines a sustainable EU Food system, but with caveats stating it is not complete, but rather points towards the need to move toward a circular understanding of complex adaptive food systems: *a sustainable food system provides and promotes safe, nutritious and healthy food of low environmental impact for all current and future EU citizens in a manner that itself also protects and restores the natural environment and its ecosystem services, is robust and resilient, economically dynamic, just and fair, and socially acceptable and inclusive. It does so without compromising the availability of nutritious and healthy food for people living outside the EU, nor impairing their natural environment*².

In the interviews we heard an immediate recognition and use of the terms ‘sustainability’ and ‘sustainable food systems.’ However, the interpretations differ. We found that there can be many. This is because

¹ Food losses and waste in the context of sustainabl food systems, HLPE FAO, 2014 <https://www.fao.org/3/i3901e/i3901e.pdf>

² A Sustainable Food System for the European Union, SAPEA, 2020: <https://www.sapea.info/wp-content/uploads/sustainable-food-system-report.pdf>

different actors in the food supply chain will have their own definition, based on where they are starting from. For business owners, sustainability might emphasize economical sustainability and to live on what they earn. For health professionals the emphasis lies much more on the nutrition and safety of food, and a food system may only seem sustainable if it ensures healthy eating patterns. While from a political perspective food security is central to sustainability and has a great value when considering the sensitivity of food systems to shocks. In the end also the social (affordability) and cultural (traditional diets) dimensions play a role when building up a sustainable food system. A complete definition of a sustainable food system seems to contain all of these dimensions and more. Sustainable Food Systems are further defined by the indicators selected.

Through the interviews and mapping our understanding of sustainability and sustainable food systems was broadened rather than condensed into a single definition. The findings from the interviews correlate very much with the key aspects named in the mapping, where depending on the stakeholders the understanding of sustainability deviate quite broadly and include a diverse range of qualitative and quantitative factors, ranging from CO₂- measurement to long lasting “sustainable” social inclusion. Still two primary themes related to sustainability could be detected which were 1) healthy eating and 2) environmental impact.

4.3 Indicators for Sustainability

Measuring sustainability is closely related to defining sustainability of the food system: the definition of a sustainable food system varies and is used flexibly, therefore, indicators also vary broadly and are always attached to the topic that a partnership/platform/network focuses on. When looking at food transactions through a systems approach many different aspects may or may not be part of measurement. Depending on the individual measurements can be interpreted as good or bad, important or unimportant - with measurements we face the problem that there is no final solution, but rather a process of trading off and compromising. There are also indicators that may be associated with one topic or category of activity (quality of food, living wages), but others that can provide insight into how the system is working across sectors (e.g. investment in R&D from public and private sectors, transparency in the food chain, policy coherence). For example, the JRC identifies indicators based on SAPEA’s working definition (defined in previous section) and also includes a ‘crosscutting’ indicator set³.

Overall, there is a need for adaptability of SFS indicators. SFS are grounded in localised activities, but also include physical and digital food environments, and globally reaching activities. Therefore, indicators must take a variety of social, economic, and political differences into account and be flexible enough to adapt to changes. Especially in situations of disruption and change, policies must imply how to diverge from indicators and which ones have the most importance in which situation. The interviewees identify a specific gap when it comes to tracking and measuring the impact on and relationship between human, nature, and health.

Another emphasis was placed on the joint profits for sustainability and affordability: The social component of a SFS must be measurable as well as the environmental component; this means making healthy sustainable food affordable and accessible while fairly financially rewarding producers for their work and minimising

³ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC126575>

harm done to people and the planet along the supply chain. Many of the indicators that emerged from the mapping are environment-related, such as the reduction of carbon emissions and the use of ingredients that come from circular or regenerative agriculture, while only one had a social component (counting the number of saved meals as an indicator). It is clear that some indicators contradict each other, but that concentrating on solely one indicator does not enable long-lasting system change. This said some aspects of the SFS are even not measurable at all or depend on certain concepts not all stakeholders share (e.g. cultural, emotional or educational efforts of food systems). Furthermore, the scale of tracking becomes important, some data may only be available very locally while other data is most appropriate to look at in aggregate at a system scale. Especially in situations of disruption and change, policies must imply how to diverge from indicators and which ones have the most importance in which situation.

Overall through the interviews and mapping we encounter many obstacles towards classic indicator setting and there seems to be a need for holistic approaches that work with many indicators at the same time while punctually highlighting those which have importance for a certain timeframe/situation/locality. Measuring a sustainable food system needs to be able to take into account different scales and indicator sets. While the broad categories might be the same at local and global scales, what data is collected and how may vary. At the local level the SFS might be concentrated on consumer-producer relationships and emerging local practices, while on a global level there is a need for data aggregation and quantification. Both quantitative data and metrics and qualitative data need to be used at multiple scales. Not all mechanisms of change may be able to be quantified or qualified: peer-to-peer relationships and trust is part of the transformation of food systems needs also be counted on when possible.

4.4 Governance Structures

Information within the ‘governance structures’ code refers to 1) governance models and ideas for the partnership and also 2) for sustainable food systems in general. For the purpose of this paper, and the development of the Food System Partnership, governance is about more than bringing people together and making decisions, it is about re-balancing power, taking action based on the inclusion of voices and opinions that might differ from each other. Establishing governance structures encompasses the questions ‘who participates? how do they participate? And who benefits from the outcomes of the decision-making process?’

A take-away regarding governance that arose from the mapping is to take all voices in the global supply chain into account: How we design governance systems has a major impact on which voices we hear. To channel and highlight voices that might not be “the usual suspect” has a high value when trying to understand barriers and shortcomings of the food system. These groups of people might not be used to the language and way of communication used in a European policy context and language and communication structures have to be adapted in order to give less visible actors an opportunity to voice concerns or wishes.

Flexibility and adaptability’ were specified as key values in a governance structure aiming to make meaningful change. They can help a partnership/organization realise a ‘shared vision’ (see chapter: Vision of Safe & Sustainable Food Systems). Interviewees also mentioned that it can help the decision-making process to ‘clearly define the topics worked on and not worked on.’ However, the majority of the input from the interviews regarding governance structures focus on inclusion and participation rather than specific decision-making processes for a partnership.

The interviewees highlighted the importance of 'listening to differing voices' and 'giving legitimacy to divergent voices' such as informal groups (e.g. neighborhood associations, social services, health centers), SMEs, processors, consumers, NGOs. All the interviewees who discussed governance spoke about including all stakeholders and several highlighted the importance of input from marginal groups and non-native citizens in the governance structure. They emphasized that 'representation is key' and that dealing with the power inequity in the food system is critical to creating governance structures for a transformed food system. Some groups need more representation and power, while others need to be coached into a new role. On this basis and with a shared vision (section 4.1) the process of discussing trade-offs and co-benefits will be different. Trade-offs will have to be made, but the burdens need to be distributed equitably and an emphasis will lie on creating shared co-benefits moving forward instead of single benefits for one stakeholder group. Governments as well have an important role to play, as they define the framework within which all the actors can move and negotiate. It is thus important for legislation to be practical, based on real-life knowledge, reflect responsibilities of stakeholder groups as well as be coherent and streamlined at the national regional and local level.

The interviewees reiterated that each partner needs to work in their sphere of influence to implement the values and targets of sustainable food system transformation.

4.5 Methodologies for Change

Four primary themes emerged from the interviews within the code 'Methodologies for change' - 1) regulation and policy development, 2) making connections throughout the whole food supply chain with a special focus on producer - consumer connection 3) influencing demand through regulation, procurement, and consumer behavior and 4) consider the environmental impact of activities, purchases, and decisions. Additionally, strong emphasis was placed on the importance of local action and aligning national planning with local planning and action. Several examples of success were given including good Samaritan laws in Italy, frameworks for urban agriculture requirements at the local level in Kenya, and the right to food of people in cities in Latin America. Additional specific activities for change included focusing on the development of fresh food markets, developing handbooks for a specific target audience, and focusing on what food choices are available where.

Some interviewees spoke about the need to describe and talk about systemic failures in order to find the levers for change, such as, procurers identifying the lack of small processing facilities. Other interviewees focused on the power of having a clear, strong, and bold vision for what a changed system looks like. Having a vision many stakeholders can identify with will require facilitated communication where supply chain actors come together as equals and all voices are heard. One surprising result from the interviews in regards to 'methodologies for change' was that several mentioned the need to not only use quantitative data and metrics, but that experiential research, storytelling, and engaging in conversations about trade-offs and benefits is critical to see change. Deep listening and tailoring activities to the local context - needs and interests - can create a 'virtuous circle' that feeds advocacy and implementation goals.

Interviewees also provide practical suggestions, such as: it is important to involve partners with differing opinions, because each one can influence a different part of the food chain, and a true system change can

only be achieved if everyone works for it. However, for this reason, there needs to be a common ground to start from (a shared vision), otherwise no partnership can be built. In order to achieve this, a skilled facilitator can be highly valuable. It can also be useful for political representatives to participate so as to give the stakeholders a feeling of reciprocity for their knowledge sharing efforts.

4.6 Needs and Gaps

From a big picture perspective, a paradigm change is needed - the European food system of today was largely created by food security concerns after WW2, which required different actions than addressing food security does now. After the war, the CAP concentrated funding on big-scale farms and nudged farms to grow and intensify production. However, the resulting production system has largely led to Europe's current food system, and moving it towards a 'sustainable' one comes with the potential of a huge loss of investments, specifically related to investments in infrastructure. Interviewees often discussed that post-production activities should take the whole system into consideration and that a redistribution and deconcentration of power of large processors and retailers along with the decision making required to change the structure requires courage to name the diversity of problems and hold the responsible stakeholders accountable.

As emphasised in the section "Vision of Safe and Sustainable Food Systems," one challenge food system change encounters is the search for a 'one size fits all' solution and one group of actors who can assume responsibility for the solution(s). By looking at food systems from a systemic perspective we understand how responsibility for change lies along the whole supply chain and there will have to be many solutions and many responsible actors for many different problems. Solutions need to address health of consumers, environmental issues, the value and quality of life of producers, and essentially engage all actors in a meaningful way. Solutions for a transition to a sustainable food system will require compromises and trade-offs and there will not be one single winner or loser.

The interviewees identified broad needs/gaps for food system transformation, such as sustainable production and business models and capacity building. They also shared insights related to needs/gaps specific to a local context, for example the legal implementation level can differ, necessitating specific interventions to be context dependent. Policy needs mentioned ranged from establishing policies where none exist to updating old/and or conflicting policies within a country. Interviewees spoke about balancing technological solutions with non-technical innovations. It follows that a huge need/gap in some countries is funding: if countries don't have funds to put practices into place, the conversations (about systems change) don't matter.

Analysis of the mapping revealed key challenges causing unsafe and unsustainable food systems, which is primarily connected to the 'needs and gaps' theme discussed by the interviewees: lack of information, trust and communication within supply chains; unjust stakeholder behavior as a result of long supply chains; and unjust access to food (overproduction in some countries vs. food insecurity in other countries); and dependencies in the food system, including power imbalances. These underscore what interviewees shared regarding the need to **address the whole system - across the supply chain - and the need to address power in the food system.**

Our analysis reveals that there is **no 'one size fits all' solution to addressing challenges and needs and gaps in food systems**. The responses to challenges in the cases we looked at and described by interviewees were quite diverse. However, one general observation is that actions conducted by networks or partnerships are either all grounded in local contexts or try to re-connect to a local context, and a key characteristic is the need for flexibility from stakeholders and interventions to adapt to the different challenges and gaps that are discovered and emerge.

5. Recommendations

This section describes the relevance of this report for future work by the FoodPathS project and the future SFS Partnership. Learning from organisations representing diverse stakeholder groups and from a variety of initiatives will help ensure the relevance of the FoodPathS project and future partnership to truly promote transformation of the food system. The recommendations underline the importance of place-based and context-specific support. For example, creating enabling environments for participation from groups, in both calls for proposals and partnership governance, that may not previously have been involved.

This section is divided into four categories: relevance for the development of the hub of a food systems lab (WP4), relevance for the development of the SRIA and RIPE (WP6), relevance for future work related to inclusivity in WP7, and relevance for the future Partnership.

5.1 Relevance of this report for the development of the hub of food system labs

FoodPathS' WP4 assesses existing public-private partnerships and initiatives at different levels (EU, regional, local) with the goal of identifying best practices and ultimately developing a concept for a 'Hub of FS Labs' to gather joint efforts and learn collectively. This report can contribute to the formation of the concept since it gives valuable insights into the variety of different opinions and stances stakeholder groups bring from different backgrounds. This understanding is vital when bringing together partnerships and projects that operate under the 'Food2030' umbrella, but have different views on differing circumstances. Bringing together stakeholders with very different views, should be seen as an opportunity to create shared visions and discuss trade-offs. For example, mutual learning to avoid trade-offs and enhance co-benefits may be enhanced by connecting with other Hubs in Europe that are culturally and globally relevant.

5.2 Relevance for this report for the development of the SRIA, RIPE and policy advice

FoodPathS' WP6 focuses on the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) for the future SFS Partnership, which should inspire diverse actors to respond to future calls for funding and innovative

projects. WP6 also focuses on addressing food system approaches to Research, Innovation, science-Policy and Education (RIPE) topics and activities. In order to ensure the mainstreaming of a food systems approach in RIPE and that diverse actors respond to calls based on the SRIA, it is critical to ensure that the activities and calls are based on topics that are relevant and respond to what different stakeholders see as needs, challenges, and opportunities. Learning from the interviews and mapping described in this report can provide guidance for future modifications of the SRIA and RIPE and fodder for discussions related to policy advice. Specific recommendations include, enable place-based responses to a call and build flexibility into the calls and processes in order to respond to learnings along the way. Encourage the development of networks regionally, national, and globally to address solutions along the entire supply chain. Focus on the development of fresh food markets and needed infrastructure (social, technical, and logistical), develop accessible handbooks for specific target audiences, and address the fact that food choices are different in different places.

5.3 Relevance for further work in WP7

This report and the results of interviewing and mapping cases will provide insights into the mirror group activities and the development of future workshops. Interviewees were asked, if they would be interested in participating in a mirror group and if they had recommendations for who else to invite, so a short list of potential participants have already been created. Topics discussed and the emerging categories will be further explored when developing workshops and engagement activities related to tasks 7.3 and 7.4. Specifically, Additionally, the toolkit developed in WP7 will respond to learnings shared in this report.

5.4 Relevance for development of the Prototype Partnership

When building up the partnership we found several key aspects that should be considered. The first one will be fair and realistic representation: Not only including the “usual suspects” that know the European context and understand the informal rules, but actively opening up to all stakeholders of the supply chain and being mindful of context & language barriers. This leads to a second key recommendation and that is that the role of facilitator is critical as they set the context for the discussions and activities. A skilled facilitator needs to balance competing interests and abilities. This entails understanding how contexts, mediums and language differ: a farmer might not have the time capacity to sit on a desk in an online meeting but would prefer a phone call so he can still tend to their other responsibilities and a grocery store manager might have other words than a researcher but still mean the same thing. When bridging these gaps, we make expert knowledge available. Practically, this means that understanding participatory processes need to account for the limitations of participants and may need to provide alternative forms of input (youth engagement) or go to where the people are (especially vulnerable groups) or rely on strong representation. This also speaks to the roles of different stakeholders, for example, governments developing policies and legislation to reach specific targets, private sector developing business plans and approaches and academics providing evidence about what works and doesn't work and acting as a neutral entity between competing interest groups.

Another key finding is the clear charge to move beyond collecting best-practices towards implementing policies that we know have an upscaling potential and broad impact. Using evidence and non-conventional forms of experiential and indigenous knowledge could be a powerful lever when looking at alternative production forms that still prove to be resistant to shocks and climate change.

Both public and private actors need to invest in research and data collection about what exactly is a sustainable food system, so that all the actors involved in the regulation and implementation have a thorough understanding of the topic before intervening to change it.

A third key-finding is the need for mindfulness of power structures. These can build up through money- and funding flows, but also through available capacity for advocacy and representation tasks, patterns and barriers in language as well as working structures and the influence of individuals that might play double-roles. When creating a governance for the partnership these informal advantages should first be identified and made formal, but when once understood can then also be a powerful tool for system transformation.

6. Annexes

Note:

These annexes belong to the Deliverable 7.1, of the European CSA project 'FOODPathS', Grant Agreement no. 101059497

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6.1 Blank mapping template

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country

One or two key features:

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:

Which ambitions and objectives:

Evolution of their governance model and organisation:

What external input and output:

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)

Main sources:
 Contact person:
 HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

.....

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

.....

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

.....

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

.....

Main sources:

Contact person:

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP

6.2 Mapped Cases WP7

Table of mapped cases

CASE	Mapped by...	Contact details
CLIMATE KIC	Cariplo	Valentina Amorese, ValentinaAmorese@fondazionecariplo.it
MILAN FOOD POLICY	Cariplo	Valentina Amorese, ValentinaAmorese@fondazionecariplo.it
MUFPP	Cariplo	Valentina Amorese, ValentinaAmorese@fondazionecariplo.it
FOOD COUNCIL BERLIN	ICLEI ES	Johanna Vordemfelde, Johanna.vordemfelde@iclei.org
ELLEN MCARTHUR FOUNDATION	ICLEI ES	Johanna Vordemfelde, Johanna.vordemfelde@iclei.org
SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS PROGRAMME	ICLEI ES	Johanna Vordemfelde, Johanna.vordemfelde@iclei.org
ORGANIC CITIES NETWORK	ICLEI ES	Johanna Vordemfelde, Johanna.vordemfelde@iclei.org
CLIMATE SMART CHEFS	Philea	Giulia Lombardi, giulia.lombardi@philea.eu
EU FOOD POLICY COALITION	Philea	Giulia Lombardi, giulia.lombardi@philea.eu
THE SUSTAINABLE RESTAURANT ASSOCIATION	Philea	Giulia Lombardi, giulia.lombardi@philea.eu
SEMENCES PAYSANNES	Philea	Giulia Lombardi, giulia.lombardi@philea.eu
EATING BETTER	Philea	Giulia Lombardi, giulia.lombardi@philea.eu
AGRITOOLKIT	INRAE	Allison-Marie Loconto, allison-marie.loconto@inrae.fr
DYTAES	INRAE	Allison-Marie Loconto, allison-marie.loconto@inrae.fr
ETIQUETTABLE	INRAE	Allison-Marie Loconto, allison-marie.loconto@inrae.fr
SFS – MED	INRAE	Allison-Marie Loconto, allison-marie.loconto@inrae.fr
SUSPNF	INRAE	Allison-Marie Loconto, allison-marie.loconto@inrae.fr
TOAM	INRAE	Allison-Marie Loconto,

SUSTAINABLE FOOD PLACES	ICLEI ES	allison-marie.loconto@inrae.fr Johanna Vordemfelde, Johanna.vordemfelde@iclei.org
4PER1000	SeaMK	Anu Palomaki, Anu.Palomaki@seamk.fi
BIOCODE	SeaMK	Anu Palomaki, Anu.Palomaki@seamk.fi
REKO NETWORK	SeaMK	Anu Palomaki, Anu.Palomaki@seamk.fi
RESQ	SeaMK	Anu Palomaki, Anu.Palomaki@seamk.fi
VEGAN CHALLENGE	SeaMK	Anu Palomaki, Anu.Palomaki@seamk.fi
NEW YORK CITY FRAMEWORK	Cariplo	Valentina Amorese, ValentinaAmorese@fondazionecariplo.it
WROCLAW	Cariplo	Valentina Amorese, ValentinaAmorese@fondazionecariplo.it

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Shifting Urban Diets: Operationalizing Food System Targets for Health and Sustainability / Copenhagen, Denmark

One or two key features:health and sustainable food system

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):running.....

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The project builds on a 2017 EIT Climate-KIC project that investigated how municipalities can develop relevant metrics and methods to identify, implement, and evaluate urban food systems interventions.

Which ambitions and objectives:The 3-year project 'Shifting Urban Diets: Operationalizing Food System Targets for Health and Sustainability' is working with the City of Copenhagen and partners to translate the findings of the EAT-Lancet Commission on Food, Planet, Health into local action and interventions

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Launched in 2019 and funded by EIT Climate-KIC, Shifting Urban Diets aims to enable cities to set smarter and more ambitious food system targets with greater accountability and measurable benefits to climate, environment, public health, and societal well-being. Shifting Urban Diets is the first initiative to operationalize the EAT-Lancet science, paving the way for a Planetary Health Diet. With Copenhagen as a prototype and other cities consulted throughout, the project will demonstrate how scientific targets for food systems can be operationalized in the city context

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food sustainability and healthy diet	City of Copenhagen, EAT Lancet Commission, EIT Climate-KIC and other research partner	relevant metrics and methods to identify, implement, and evaluate urban food systems interventions	Changing in citizens habits	Support from the local Municipality	New food habits that are more sustainable and safer for the planet and society as well as smart indicators to measure implement, and evaluate urban food systems interventions	

.....the fact that the Milan Municipality has a dedicated direction for the local food policy makes this practice extremely resilient and sustainable

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The main strength of the Copenhagen initiative lies in the support from the Municipality as well as the cultural and social framework in which it is developed, but also the presence of valuable research institutions		The diversity of the actors in the project contribute to make it a success	Actors lay different role but all actors contribute in defining the final goals	Open interaction between partners

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

In order to be carried out this project requires a cultural and social contest that recognize the relevance of the problem as well as funding and time to be developed. The municipality needs to be engaged in the first place.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The practice was developed to make the local Food system more safe and sustainable for the planet and citizens

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Actors from different background are gathered together and attention is given to indicators and new form of data analysis.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The project aims to set smarter and more ambitious food system targets with greater accountability and measurable benefits to climate, environment, public health, and societal well-being.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Food Policy / Italy

One or two key features:health and sustainable food

system.....

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):running.....

Photo banner (including country)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The Food Policy is the city's food policy. It represents one of the legacies of Expo 2015, and is a support tool for city government promoted in synergy by the Municipality of Milan and the Cariplo Foundation to make the Milanese food system more sustainable

Which ambitions and objectives: 1. ensure healthy food for all 2. promote the sustainability of the food system 3. educate about food 4. fight against waste 5. scientific research

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: the Milan Food Policy was launched in 2015 and gradually entered the municipality governance moving from an office in the municipality to become a direction

What external input and output:

https://youtu.be/tr_vCYQh1LU?list=PLHd5UJ5aE67pcy59XCbPTFrleQmndwgxk

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food sustainability and healthy diet	Milan Municipality, NGOs, Foundations, Researchers, civil society	Projects, new policies and regulations	Projects, events, community of practices, network	Support from the Milan Municipality Governance and of Cariplo Foundation as neutral actor	New projects, new local hubs, new regulations and new policies	Actions can last from few months up to many years

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The main strength of the Milan Food Policy lies in long term engagement of the Milan Municipality and Cariplo Foundation	The Milan Food Policy can not be considered a flexible actor but it enjoys Cariplo Foundation's flexibility while can benefit from the strategic relevance of the Milan Municipality	The main strength of the Milan Food Policy lies in the ability to create connections between all actors of the Milan Urban Food System	Cariplo Foundation and Milan Municipality jointly define their goals every years	Milan Food Policy interacts with other Municipalities all over the world to share and transfer local best practices on sustainable food system

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The practice was developed in order to foster the development of a more sustainable food system in the city of Milan

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

The practice started with the mapping activity of the food system and the development of a government approach that included two main actors (Milan Municipality and Cariplo Foundation) and gradually starting from this it was developed a policy for the city and a network that sees the participation of many different actors from different food system areas.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

We developed a number of indicators related to the different projects that characterize the food policy. There is no single indicator. We have indicator to measure impact of dietary change in terms of CO2 production for example. Indicator on the number of actors active in the policy etc etc

Name of the food systems co-creation case / CountryMilan Pact Award
 One or two key features:foster sustainable food systems
 Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):running.....

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors One of the most important goals of the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP), is to stimulate the exchange of practices and learning between signatory cities. To foster this collaboration since 2016 the City of Milan and the Cariplo Foundation launched the Milan Pact Awards (MPA) with the aim of recognizing the most creative efforts and monitoring which cities were implementing the commitments they had made when they joined the pact. The awards are a means of encouraging action, facilitating the emergence of the best practices of the MUFPP cities, making them evident to the community with a function of inspiring the action of other signatory cities

Which ambitions and objectives: To foster the collaboration between MUFPP cities and Cariplo Foundation strength local urban food systems

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: since the begging Cariplo Foundation and the Milan Municipality worked together on the Award

What external input and output:

<https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/award/>

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
International	Municipalities	New best practices and new food policies	Rewarding best practices	Awards (50k annually contribution + in kind engagement of local actors)	New best practices and new food policies, new signatories cities for the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact	The Award has been launched annually or every 2 years

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The award represents an inspiration and a model for others grant making organization engaged on food policies . The awards represent an achievement for all municipalities active on food policies		Actors thanks to the Milan secretary interacts internationally	1. Governance 2. Sustainable diets and nutrition 3. Social and economic equity 4. food production 5. food supply and distribution 6. food waste	International collaboration across municipalities

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

For it's sustainability it requires the engagement of Cariplo Foundation and the Milan Municipality

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

This activity overcome geographical differences creating a network that shares information, knowledge and best practices all around the world. During COVID pandemic this action has been extremely important as it allowed for sharing emergency answers to similar problems. In general, this action is crucial because it allow to not replicate errors fostering food system transformation all around the world in an inclusive and open way.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

The practice does requires certain funding and some level of engagement and in kind contribution from the actors supporting it.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

There are more than 250 practices collected in over 6 years. I would say this is the most relevant indicator

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Food Council Berlin/Germany
One or two key features: network of citizens to influence urban food policy
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

Which ambitions and objectives: in a local food strategy the food council Berlin developed guidelines for a local sustainable food system, along the whole value-chain, now it is in the process of realizing this strategy

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The food council Berlin is made up of different entities, the board of directors and the circle of speakers who all represent one working group with a specific food related topic

What external input and output: the food council Berlin works in different structures: allows citizens to engage, appears as entity in EU-projects and interacts closely with the local government. Therefore the external in- and output is high.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Local food system Berlin	Citizens, local politicians, local and international NGO's and research (secondary actor)	mainly local action in close cooperation with citizens, local food strategy, part of FoodCLIC (EU project)	open discussion and city dialogue on transformation of the local food system → followed by implication in projects or political lobbying activities	Dependent on external funding such as EU- or local funding, dependent on citizen engagement, dependent on "openness" from the local government towards a change in food policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a concrete food strategy paper • funding for a FoodCampus • Book Release "Berlin isst anders" • action-focused conference on the local food system 	founded in 2016; since app. 2 - 3 years a player in european food policy and project management

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> many years of experience in citizen engagement activism coupled with scientific skills internationally renowned and included in european networks/research projects 	very high level of flexibility towards citizens and their needs in terms of local food systems → work with a democratic bottom - up approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network activities with other german food councils included in EU-projects → therefore interaction with european partners self-understanding of being a platform for all stakeholders of the local food system interaction with local government 	The cluster, as in "all engaged stakeholders of local value chains", has the joint goal to transform the regional food system and value-chain towards more sustainability, equality and fairness	Tries to set up a "Network of Food Councils" for Germany, but the funding stopped; also coach other civil entities who want to build up food councils and support them

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Very action focused, both on a local as on a european level. The process they make towards sustainability is to be considered quite big, with their impact on Berlin food policies through their food strategy paper as well as their international impact through Horizon-projects. The Food Council Berlin has paid staff instead of a being reliant on volunteers which enhances their influence and efficiency. One good example is the planned food-Campus, which is a mayor project to connect citizens to learn and discuss about food and also the "LebensMittelPunkte" which are local food-distribution and gathering- spaces

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

It addresses global value-chains and focuses on regional food consumption. Also concentrates on food inequalities inside cites, local infrastructure problems (such as "LebensMittelPunkte"), unsustainable public procurement practices, food loss and unsustainable packaging, and so on; they really focus on every part of the value chain

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Specific projects are implemented after collecting citizens and local stakeholders views, such as a FoodCampus, local distribution and gathering points ("LebensMittelPunkte") and lobbying activities.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

They see sustainable food chains as closely linked to equality. Both can just be implemented together, eg. a sustainable value chain ist also a just, democratic and inclusive value chain without power centralization.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Ellen MacArthur Foundation
 One or two key features: City Self Assessment to understand specific solutions in the area of food/circular economy
 Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The foundation brings together industry leading corporations, emerging innovators, affiliate Networks, government authorities, regions and cities in their "Network", where they have open discussion, share knowledge and experience. All dedicated to the topic of circular economy.

Which ambitions and objectives: The objective of the City Self Assessment is to help cities analyse their current state of the city food system and to subsequently find out in which areas a city could approve

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The Foundation was built up by Ellen MacArthur (fastes solo sailor to sail around the world) to enhance circular economy and is now supported by different partners such as BlackRock, Danone, Gucci, H&M, Ikea, Intesa SanPaolo, Nestle, Coca-Cola, Unilever

What external input and output:

External input of expert knowledge by partners; Largest Congress for circular Economy and networking activities inside the crucial industry as an output; other outputs are education and learning resources openly accessible on the website as well as tools and guidance for businesses

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
City Food System	Municipalities	knowledge, advise, assessment	Analysing the current Food System	Assessed cities must have knowledge and data about the city food system	very precise advise on how to make the Food system more circular	Filling out the assessment form when data are complete: 15 Minutes

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The Foundation and the network have insights and expert knowledge on innovation, business and research in circular economy	The Foundation is in any case a very inclusive actor towards all sectors (industry, research, cities, etc.)	Yes! As explained above.	The Foundation defines a certain goal (circular economy) and gathers partners that support this goal while having other own goals (eg. sales, marketing, etc.)	The Foundation looks at all sectors through the lenses of circular economy

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The Foundations ratio is quite big since big players of the food industry are partners. Their Network is also big (100+ partners) and the conference is well-known in the circular economy "bubble". The willingness to take action comes from the founders own experience of sailing around the earth with a finite of resources, which she applies to global economy. Her goal is to make economy circular by design, not just by recycling: All products must be designed to be reused in another way after their time is up. In terms of food this means using all parts of a food (reduction of food waste) and using the food waste as fuel (reusing of food waste).

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

- Food Waste inside the production chain: Many "parts" of live stock, plants, crops are not used to feed humans, which leads to an unsustainable over-production.
- Packaging: Not all Cities have established an sufficient recycling system
- Transportation: Food is shipped from overseas, poor infrastructure for regional food commerce, regional food production is unable to produce sufficient foods

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

This case deals mainly with the topic of circular economy and food systems. Therefore, the main focus lies in creating nature-positive foods, regenerative food production and reduction or recycling of packaging. nature-positive foods means foods that use ingredients that come from regenerative agriculture or are upcycled (eg. cookies hade from left-over flour from plant-based milk production, cocoa fruit pulp, crop leftovers). In regard to the City self assessment also the topic of regional sale structures for foods is an important topic.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The main focus is circularity: The Sustainable Food Systems gives back as much to nature and soil as it takes out. All waste and packaging is recycled.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: One Planet Network, Sustainable Food Systems Programme
One or two key features: the network is a multi-stakeholder international initiatives that unites cities, enterprises, NGOs etc
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

Which ambitions and objectives: catalyzing urgent transformation towards sustainable food systems, as a critical strategy to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The SFS Programme (SFSP) is part of the broader One Planet Network (OPN): the network that created six sustainability programmes to implement the United Nations 10-Year Framework of Programmes on Sustainable Consumption and Production (10YFP), which were created by the Heads of State at the Rio+20 UN Conference on Sustainable Development in 2012. The multi-actor AgriFood Task Force prepared the launch of the 10YFP on SFS, which was officially launched in 2015 as SDG target 12.1. The 10YFP was renamed as the OPN in 2017. In 2022, and following the the UN Secretary General’s Food System Summit in 2021, the OPN-SFSP aims to build synergies and nurture cooperation among a wide array of actors and initiatives by supporting the implementation of the Commitments, Action Areas and Coalitions created during the UNFSS.

What external input and output: The outputs are awareness raising on food security and nutrition topics, building capacity and enable conditions for food systems to adapt sustainable practices, tools and methodologies to support governments in the transformation process and partnership building

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
the network engages on all levels due to regional as well as international partnerships and bring together “unusual allies”	everyone involved in food; with a special focus on regional governments	knowledge, best-practice, education, collaboration, experience and expertise	advocacy and conceptual as well as action-oriented work implemented by collaborative initiatives at global, regional and national/local levels	the network stays on a very theoretical meta-level	Bi-yearly conference on Sustainable Food Systems development and next steps; Tools such as E-Learning, case studies; research on Multi-Stakeholder Mechanisms as a possibility for system change → bringing together unusual allies with a whole system approach	2012-2015 : Agrifood Task Force 2017-2022 : One Planet network 2022 – ... : UNFSS follow-up

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Tackling interrelated challenges by using a system-based approach and including multiple actors	Very adaptive towards players in the food sector as well as to new challenges; including "unusual allies" is an incentive	the network fosters "multi-stakeholder mechanisms" such as food councils, sustainable food labs, which then try to embed transformation locally	yes: providing healthy diets while staying within the planetary boundaries	The One Planet network launched other programmes: consumer information on sus consumption, sus. Buildings & Construction, Sus. Lifestyles & Education, Sus. Public Procurement and Sus. Tourism

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Their key accomplishment is a multi-actor consensus, by industry as well as regional governments, NGOs or other stakeholders, that the food system is in need of a systemic approach when looking at new solutions. Here lies a great sustainability in the sense that solutions are not forced onto a system, but the stakeholders jointly discuss and build up those changes → the approach is highly inclusive and therefore likely to introduce sustainable and lasting changes

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

There is a strong focus on healthy and affordable diets - which 40% of global population cannot afford in 2020 leading to growing inequality due to growing power imbalances among food system actors - while respecting the planets boundaries. Food waste as a driver of food insecurity and unsustainability is also another key focus of the programme.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Awareness raising on food security and nutrition topics, building capacity and enable conditions for food systems to adapt sustainable practices, tools and methodologies to support governments in the transformation process and partnership building

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

inclusive, diverse, resilient, healthy and environmentally sustainable → a broad whole system approach to sustainability including health and equality

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Organic Cities Europe/Europe

One or two key features: network of organic cities → municipalities who advance on the topic of sustainable city food systems

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running

DESCRIPTION

Which ambitions and objectives: Umbrella organization for all organic cities in Europe; making their goals and ambitions visible on an international scale

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: In 2002 the network is founded in Italy with a focus on rural development and territories, a cultural model beyond merely agricultural cultivation, quality and artisanal production, regionalism and sustainability, education and food waste

What external input and output: builds up on the work of the european organic cities, therefore regional work can be seen as an input to the european network; outputs are events, talks and lobbying activities

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
European level; agricultural policy	organic cities representants (administration), local & european policy makers	Urban Food Systems	Networking; knowledge & experience exchange	Dependent on the existence and participation of local organic cities → dependence on local governments	exchange on enhancing food system sustainability	ongoing since 2002 → over 20 years

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Connections to policymakers on an european level; voice on an european level	The actor is made up of sub-actors (regional organic cities) and therefore adapts to their activities and wishes; does not adapt to cities/actors unwilling to become an organic city	actors form a network and trust the organic cities network with european representation	defined goal is to: foster regional structures for organic production and procurement/ promoting & sharing best-practice in regional organic farming	the network works with european policymakers and the regional organic cities are implemented into the cities administration and therefore closely connected to all other departments → especially education departments for the topic of procurement

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The network is made up of several actors that present a different level of willingness to take action, also there are two further networks collected under the umbrella "Organic Cities Network Europe" which are the " Città del Bio" and the "BioStädte Netzwerk", who are very active in their own area. Therefore one might say the willingness of the actors is very high, but the actual european network does not have the resources or personnel to really work on topic-related projects, but is rather the organ for representation on an european level.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

This case concentrates on the differences between regional organic and global conventional food production. In the networks view the unsustainable circumstances of the Food Systems are mostly global transportation, declining regional food security and growing practices of food not produced by ecological criteria.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

The network mostly wants to promote the possibility of becoming a organic city to other cities, municipalities and regions. Organic Cities work - from the policymaker and administration side - on transforming the regional Food System in order to enhance the production and consumption of ecological foods. Also the network promotes the idea of the organic city movement to European & International Policymakers.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The indicator used here is the european label for organic food production and its criteria.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country

Climate Smart Chefs

One or two key features:

promotion of low emission, nutritious and affordable diets

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

Running (01/01/2022 – 31/12/2024)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:

The LIFE CLIMATE SMART CHEFS is a European project receiving funding from the LIFE Programme of the European Union. It aims to contribute to the development and implementation of the EU Climate Policy and the Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy. Project partners are one philanthropic funder, world's leading educational and training centre for the Italian food and beverage and hospitality sectors, the largest networks of Vocational Education and Training providers in Italy, a university, menu management software company.

Which ambitions and objectives:

The main project objectives are:

- To increase the awareness on the relationship between food and climate change at the EU level.
- To engage chefs as active changemakers and promoters of low emission, nutritious and affordable diets in the EU.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Thanks to the project's activities a Network of Life Climate Smart Chefs has been created made of chef associations, restaurants, hotels and caterers who will engage in the fight against food waste, reducing carbon emissions and water consumption: [The network - Life Climate Smart Chefs](#)

What external input and output:

- the implementation of a high-level training course for chefs
- the development of a digital tool to design climate smart menus
- the creation of an Award dedicated to climate smart chefs and local initiatives promoting sustainable diets
- the creation of an EU Network of chef associations
- the implementation of the Life Climate Smart Chefs Vision 2030, a strategic paper aimed at providing policy recommendations and supporting EU Climate Policy.

[Home - Life Climate Smart Chefs](#)

[CSC-brochure-ENG-02 \(climatesmartchefs.eu\)](#)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food sustainability and healthy diets	Vocational training institutes in the hospitality sectors, universities, IT companies, chef associations, restaurants, hotels and caterers.	An high-level training course, digital tools, an award, a strategic paper.	Creating a stable network of chefs working in restaurants and catering companies committed to food sustainability.	Make food businesses and their customers to make more informed and environmentally-conscious decision	Raising awareness among chefs on the importance of food sustainability and at the same time enhancing their skills and competencies in preparing healthy and sustainable menus.	Duration of the LIFE project: 01/01/2022 – 31/12/2024

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
<p>Chefs are provided a training on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Why food is important for our planet's future and for solving climate change. - How to reduce food waste and save money - How to communicate the value of sustainability with your staff, suppliers and customersow to use a specially designed menu engineering tool to create menus that are healthy, affordable and good for the planet. 	<p>The training activities provided through this project are open to any chef interested in the topic despite its affiliation to a company or association part of the network.</p>	<p>The partnership sees very diverse partners from the vocational training, IT and hospitality sector coming together and share expertise/ develop skills.</p>	<p>The main goal is to provide turn chefs in active promoters of sustainable diets and encourage them to communicate and disseminate science-based information.</p>	<p>The project was able to mobilise caterers and chefs associations in one year. The challenge will be to maintain this mobilisation beyond the end of the project.</p>

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision-making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Within this projects, chefs are identified as potential active changemakers and promoters of low emission, nutritious and affordable diets in the EU.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Unsustainable and unhealthy diets in the hospitality sector.
Food loss and waste in the hospitality sector.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

One of the action, beyond the ones mentioned above, is the he implementation of the Life Climate Smart Chefs Vision 2030, a strategic paper aimed at providing policy recommendations.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The project is promoting the 'Foodprint' too is a fully automated, easy-to-use environmental impact scoring, display, and emission reporting system for the hospitality and food service (HaFS) sector. The aim is to combines the latest research with cutting-edge technology to support chefs and organisations on their journey to carbon neutrality.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Eating Better, United Kingdom

One or two key features: Growing network to accelerate a shift to a sustainable and healthier food system, with “less and better” meat and more plants.

Status: Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The power of the alliance comes from its breadth, diversity and expertise. From environmental and animal welfare charities to public health and social justice, Eating Better is working to create a fair and sustainable food environment, where everyone has access to healthy, affordable and nutritious food. The focus is ‘less and better’ meat and more plants, which is better for humanity, for nature and for the planet.

Which ambitions and objectives: Eating Better’s goal is to halve meat and dairy consumption in the UK by the end of this crucial decade of action to reduce GHG emissions, protect nature and get us all eating better.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Eating Better raise funds for its work from supporter organisations, trusts, foundations, and individuals. It does not seek or accept funds directly from commercial organisations. Trustees are responsible for approving all major grant applications.

What external input and output: Eating Better draws on the experience and expertise of the alliance to accelerate transformational change in the way society produces and consumes food. Eating Better works across the food system from farm to table, collaborating with and influencing civil society, local and central government, food retail, food service, farmers, academia and investors. Collectively and collaboratively the alliance works to make food part of the solution to the climate, nature and health crises.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
The Eating Better alliance is working to stimulate a 50% reduction in meat and dairy consumption in the UK by 2030, and for a transition to ‘better’ meat and dairy as standard.	Government, Producers, Food retail, Food service, Investors.	A roadmap to less and better meat and dairy, providing 24 actions to be taken across 5 sectors to create an enabling environment to drive the necessary transformation in eating habits.	24 actions to be taken across 5 sectors – e.g. (I) Deliver a cross-departmental food and farming strategy; (II) Harness opportunities for more plant production; (III) Embed a sustainable diets strategy across the business; (IV) Put more plants on plates and menus; (V) Engage to promote healthy and sustainable production.	Through data-driven reports and analysis of food trends Eating Better tracks progress, calling out inaction and demand more of those lagging behind in promoting sustainable and balanced diets.	In 2022, Eating Better made great strides to improve understanding of the food system, track progress, influence the agenda for change, grow the alliance and to showcase positive practices in producing and serving less and better meat and dairy in line with the Better by Half roadmap.	Short, medium and long-term, with the aim of stimulating a 50% reduction in meat and dairy consumption in the UK by 2030.

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Clear actions are provided by Eating Better to accelerate the transition from producing and eating too much meat and dairy to a fairer, healthier and more sustainable food system.	Flexible, Eating Better is regularly reaching out to new stakeholders to grow in influence, and to bring new voices into the alliance.	The alliance brings together a wide array of actors from different sectors.	The alliance members collectively and collaborative work to make food part of the solution to the climate, nature and health crisis.	Works with other Partner Networks such as the 'European Public Health Alliance' or the 'Food Research Collaboration'.

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Eating Better's survey on retailer tactic around meat found that the retailers are not matching their rhetoric on sustainable eating with action to reduce meat productions.

Another surveys highlighted that 86% of members have used Eating Better's resources to support their work over the last two years.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Food systems are associated with roughly 42% of global greenhouse gas emissions according to the IPP WG3, April 2022 report, with livestock farming a major contributor. Meat from ruminants such as sheep and cows have the highest GHG intensity. Moreover, producing meat and dairy takes up swathes of land with half of the world's habitable land being used for agriculture with more than three-quarters of this used for livestock production, while contributing only 37% of the protein in the global food supply. Intensive agriculture is the also the biggest driver of habitat and wildlife loss, while crowded conditions for farmed animals are potential breeding grounds for dangerous pathogens and emerging pandemics, risking public health.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Eating Better works across the food system from farm to table, collaborating with and influencing civil society, local and central government, food retail, food service, farmers, academia and investors. It has developed the 'Better By Half' roadmap, which identifies 24 actions across five influential sectors, where change needs to happen to ensure everyone has access to healthy, nutritious and affordable food.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Numbers of supporting organisations and partner networks; digital engagement (e.g. hours watched on YouTube, website visitors, LinkedIn views).

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: EU Food Policy Coalition / Europe

One or two key features: Participants in the EU Food Policy Coalition work towards policy integration and alignment at the EU-level to facilitate the transition to sustainable food systems. The Coalition provides the debating space to discuss policies and, sometimes, carry out joint activities.

Status: Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:The Coalition brings together civil society and organisations working towards refining and advocating for a shared vision of sustainable food systems at the EU level such as: NGOs from a broad spectrum working on food systems, grassroots social movements, farmers organisations, organisations of fishers, trade unions, think tanks, scientific and research groups.

Which ambitions and objectives:Participants in the EU Food Policy Coalition work towards policy integration and alignment at the EU-level to facilitate the transition to sustainable food systems. The Coalition provides the debating space to discuss policies and, sometimes, carry out joint activities.

What external input and output:The report Towards a Common Food Policy for the EU, captures the objectives and priorities co-constructed by a wide range of actors, and constitutes the document that crystallises the overarching policy vision of the Coalition.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Transition to sustainable food systems	NGOs from a broad spectrum working on food systems, grassroots social movements, farmers organisations, organisations of fishers, trade unions, think tanks, scientific and research groups.	The Coalition provides the debating space to discuss policies and, sometimes, carry out joint activities.	Participants in the Coalition work towards policy integration and alignment at the EU-level to facilitate the transition to sustainable food systems.	An integrated food policy can reclaim public policy for the public good, rebuild public confidence in the European project, and put the EU on track to meet the SDGs and the Paris Climate Agreement.	Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections, endorsed by 26 organisations + Open letter on the need for a strong proposal on an EU legislative framework for sustainable food systems, endorsed by 286 organisations	Short, medium and long term

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Broad coalition bringing together different actors.	Flexible, the coalition provides the debating space to discuss policy, and take joint activities.	Different actors involved, NGOs, Grassroots social movements, farmers organizations, think tanks, trade unions, research groups	Involved actors can decide autonomously whether to endorse the outputs that have emerged from internal debates (e.g. Elections Manifesto – Our Food, Our Health, Our Planet)	Closely linked to biodiversity loss, climate change and social justice but no joint objectives with other clusters

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Actors are involved, as seen by the high number of endorsement, 286, for the open letter on the need for a strong proposal on an EU legislative framework for sustainable food systems.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Food systems are pushing us across 'planetary boundaries', driving diet-related diseases and failing to deliver decent livelihoods in the EU and beyond: they are therefore at the heart of the change that citizens are asking for. EU policies, and in particular the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), have so far failed to drive a transition towards sustainable food systems.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

- March 2023: Elections Manifesto – Our Food, Our Health, Our Planet
- February 2023: Open letter on the need for a strong proposal on an EU legislative framework for sustainable food systems
- October 2022: Manifesto for establishing Minimum Standards for Public Canteens across the EU

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Inclusive, transparent, socially and economically just food system

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country The Sustainable Restaurant Association, United Kingdom
One or two key features: The SRA believes food service businesses can have a restorative impact on the planet.
Status: Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: To accelerate change towards an environmentally restorative and socially progressive hospitality sector, the SRA works with businesses from across foodservice, as well as like-minded industry bodies, campaign groups and businesses that supply the sector through its signature programme, Food Made Good.

Which ambitions and objectives: Bring together progressive people working in the food sector & empower them to change the system faster.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Sitting at the intersection between foodservice and the sustainable food movement, the SRA defines sustainability for the sector, assesses behavior, measures action and celebrates progress.

What external input and output: The Food Made Good online community is a thriving space where businesses can connect to seek solutions for their sustainability challenges, share successes and communicate with like-minded individuals who are committed to meeting the same goals. Issue specific conversations and threads, alongside the portfolio of accompanying tools and resources provide users with a genuine depth of support on their journey.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Accelerate change toward an environmentally restorative and socially progressive hospitality sector.	Foodservice providers.	Food Made Good is the most globally recognised industry standard for measuring sustainability across the Hospitality Sector.	Promotes and measures action through the industry standard sustainability certification, the Food Made Good Rating + Encourage best practice and inspire healthy competition.	Being part of a global movement and working together with other foodservice providers to build a more sustainable future.	What began as a membership organisation with 50 founding members has grown into a global movement of more than 10,000 kitchens. It is a very diverse community of food service businesses, from high end to high street, from street-food staples to workplace canteens, from independent cafes to Michelin starred restaurants, all working to make sustainability part of their DNA.	Short, medium and long term.

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
SRA provides continual support to advance foodservice businesses environmental and social responsibility	Flexible, actors adapt their strategies to achieve the sustainability objectives laid out in the 'Food Made Good' framework	Actors act individually, but they are intrinsically part of a wider movement with the opportunity for each actors to connect and seek solutions for their sustainability challenges	Goal is already laid out in the 'Food Made Good' framework	Food retailers and Food suppliers working jointly

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The rapid increase in membership, which now exceeds 10,000, is evidence of the growing involvement of foodservice providers.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Greenhouse gas emissions from meat and dairy production, food waste, single-use plastic.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

SRA aims to accelerate change towards a food sector that is socially progressive and environmentally restorative by connecting progressive people and businesses both in the UK and across the globe through the Food Made Good programme.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

- Number of foodservice providers joining the 'Food Made Good' programme
- Improvements in 'sustainable rating' of foodservice providers over time

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Mit Eszel? platform/ Hungary
One or two key features: Farm sustainability assessment system and consumer information platform
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Based on the AgriToolKit sustainability tool, Mit Eszel? platform was developed as an interactive, customer-supported, quality assurance system. The Agri Toolkit was developed by Agri Kult in collaboration with farmers and consumers. As a group of environmental consultants and innovators, Agrikulti has more than 10 years of experience with natural and social science research and development of sustainable food systems, farmers markets, farmers and consumers.

Which ambitions and objectives: The most important goal is to strengthen city-rural relations by building short supply chains that are both ecologically and economically viable. Mit Eszel? trademark was registered in order to provide customers with information about sustainably operating farms. The platform also aims to encourage consumers to visit nearby farms to interact with the producers of their food and better understand where the food they eat comes from and how its production affects the environment around us. Agri Toolkit is a science based, complex and easy to interpret farming sustainability assessment tool. The system considers farming activities and does not measure physical, chemical or biological outcome variables. The Green Test is the consumer friendly version developed for farm visits.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: AgriKulti is a small non-profit company and social enterprise. It participates in European research, innovation and coordination actions. AgriKulti has launched a number of innovative initiatives to build

What external input and output: AgriKulti has received funding from EU projects and the Hungarian Ministry of Agriculture to develop the AgriToolKit and the Mit Eszel? platform. The AgriToolKit indicators are based on the FAO's Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture systems (SAFA) guidelines. AgriKulti issues certificates for farms that pass the evaluation.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Hungary is experiencing significant rural to urban migration, with a major cause being rural unemployment Government supporting agrobiodiversity and agroecology	Farmers, Consumers, Researchers, Environmentalists	Fresh vegetables, Pulses, Ancient cereals	Innovations: Nagymaros Farmers Market Házikó farm-to-table restaurant/factory a farm sustainability assessment tool, a consumer platform	National agroecology policy – promoting traditional varieties and breeds EU Organic standard	Functioning farmers market in the centre of Budapest Lessons learned about economic sustainability from Farm-to-table restaurant (40 farmers served 300 partners, 12 employees) New living lab on neglected legumes	2010 – AgriKulti created 2011 – Nagymaros Farmers market started 2014-2018 - Házikó running 2020 – AgriToolKit + Green Test

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
AgriKulti – knowledge about sustainable food systems	Flexible – Adapting to different innovations and opportunities to create sustainable food systems	Networked domestically and internationally (EU)	Yes – working on a definition of agroecology for Senegal	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems
Consumers Association (Association of Conscious Consumers (ACC)/Hungarian Tudatos Vásárlók Egyesülete (TVE)) – consumer knowledge/demand	Flexible – consumer campaigns and behaviour change programs to support solidarity based food systems	Cluster of consumers, but networked with farmers and advisors	Yes – healthy diets for the Senegalese	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems
Farmers – traditional knowledge and organic knowledge	Flexible – adapts to climate and market pressures	Clustered through local chapters of farmer groups	Sometimes – not all farmers have the same goal	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems
Ministry of Agriculture – political will and financing of short circuit food chains	Semi-flexible – adapts to include agroecology and local food systems into national policy	Networked with the researcher experts and the EU	Sometimes – the government seeks to reduce unemployment and increase food sovereignty	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems
European Union - funding	Flexible – EU funding of research opens more avenues for innovation	Networked across the EU	Yes – EU Green Deal and SDGs	Yes – local, solidarity-based and sustainable food systems

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

AgriKulti has been leading, and at times following, their partners through a number of experimentations and innovations seeking to create local food systems that link Budapest with the surrounding rural areas. Their status as a social enterprise and their willingness to risk personal private and public funds to advance the ideas demonstrates a strong feeling of responsibility for changing current food systems.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The challenges of a lack of national food sovereignty and rural unemployment were the original drivers of the need to change the Food System. The promotion of agroecology and the support for traditional breeds and agrobiodiversity by the Ministry of Agriculture has offered a means for local innovators to become more active. The Covid crisis and the Russian-Ukrainian war have highlighted the importance of strengthening the resilience and autonomy of food systems, particularly in Eastern Europe. The lack of diversity in both agriculture and markets have revealed the unsustainability of food systems in Hungary.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

AgriKulti is but one actor within an expanding network of innovators who are testing new ways of linking farmers and consumers. The approach, which is based on linking scientific knowledge with farmers' knowledge and consumers' knowledge has brought these actors into closer collaboration. The development of metrics, simple evaluations and labels enable greater transparency about the origin of food in Budapest.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The evaluation system takes into account the economic decisions. Specifically, the diversity of cultivated varieties, the impact of farming technologies on wildlife, the climate, and the soil; material and energy use, animal welfare and water use, and the impact on the local economy. The initiative contributes to SDGs 2, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 15.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Dynamics for an Agroecological Transition in Senegal " (DyTAES) / Senegal
One or two key features: National multi-stakeholder network that is driven by farmers and researchers.
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The "Dynamics for an Agroecological Transition in Senegal " (DyTAES) is a network that was created in 2019. It brings together organizations of producers, consumers, rural women, NGOs, research institutions, civil society networks, a network of local elected officials and companies. An annual Caravan that carried out workshops across all agroecological zones enabled a co-creation of the national platform and national level policy recommendations. Because of the interest of Mayors and local officials, and thanks to the decentralisation of the state more broadly, DyTAELs (local dynamics) began to be formed in 2021 and represent the future focus of the DyTAES.

Which ambitions and objectives: DyTAES has the aim of promoting an agroecological transition in Senegal through advocacy, awareness-raising, sharing of experience and support for territories in transition.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The DyTAES is made up of colleges representing the different stakeholder groups nationally and in each territory.

What external input and output: The diagnostic analysis and the political recommendations delivered to the Ministers of Agriculture and the Environment were developed based on a participatory consultation process that included more than 1.000 actors from 6 agroecological zones of Senegal (territorial workshops) and from Dakar (consumer workshops). The process has been supported by French and Senegalese researchers, European donors and intergovernmental organisations (ECOWAS and FAO).

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
<p>First Government of Macky Sall named the "agroecological transition" the third pillar of its political programme</p> <p>Public controversies around pesticides poisoning</p>	<p>Farmers Orgs, international and national NGOs, French and national research institutes, Donors, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Environment, FAO</p>	<p>Fresh vegetables (onions, carrots, cabbage, eggplants), 'agroecological technical packages', knowledge</p>	<p>Farmer training, Creation of a national platform, Creation of local platforms, Agroecological Caravan, Annual Agroecology Day, Agroecology restaurant in Thies, Box schemes</p>	<p>Government decentralization (Agriculture and Environment Advisors at District level)</p> <p>Organic manure included in government subsidies</p> <p>ECOWAS and FAO 10 programme planning on agroecology</p>	<p>National platform that includes all stakeholders</p> <p>Local platforms for local action</p> <p>Ongoing multi-stakeholder policy dialogue</p> <p>Topic specific policy briefs</p>	<p>2019 – creation of the DyTAES</p> <p>2021 – creation of the first DyTAEL</p> <p>2023 – 3rd caravan</p>

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Researchers – knowledge about agroecology	Flexible – Adapting to different agro-ecological zones	Networked domestically and internationally (EU)	Yes – working on a definition of agroecology for Senegal	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
Consumers Association (CICODEV) – consumer demand	Flexible – adapting consumer campaigns to healthy and agroecological food	Cluster of consumers, but networked with NGOs	Yes – healthy diets for the Senegalese	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
CNCR (Farmers Union) – traditional knowledge and political influence	Flexible – adapts to climate and market pressures	Clustered through local chapters of farmer groups	Sometimes – not all farmers have the same goal	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
Ministries of Agriculture and Environment – political will	Semi-flexible – adapts to include the DyTAES in a policy dialogue, but dependent on government policy	Networked with the researcher experts, Donors, Farmers Union and NGOs	Sometimes – the government seeks to reduce food insecurity and adapt to climate-change. Agroecology is seen as 'reforestation'	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
NGOs – complementary projects, knowledge	Semi-flexible – combines interest for some common advocacy, but competes for donor funding	Networked within DyTAES	Sometimes – not all NGOs share the same mission and have different visions of agroecology	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
Donors - funding	Inflexible – Donor funding is tied to donor priorities	Usually 1-1 interactions	No – each donor has its own goal in line with its national/organisational strategy	Yes – agroecological transition for the country
Private sector – markets, legitimacy	Flexible – New markets for bioinputs emerging	Clustered , but not organised in an interprofession	Sometimes – they will also sell agrochemicals and junk food	Maybe – it depends on the interests of each company

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The remarkable aspect of the DyTAES (and the DyTAELs) is that all of the actors have assumed responsibility for a sustainability transition. The co-creation process that is inclusive not just of all types of actors, but also of all agroecological zones across the country is promising. The annual caravan offers a strong model for regional consultations.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The challenges of a lack of food sovereignty and youth unemployment in a context of climate change is the core circumstance of unsustainability. Faced with the widespread degradation of natural resources (water, soil, forests, etc.), agroecology makes it possible to rethink in depth our ways of producing, exchanging and consuming in order to build a new development model. The Covid crisis and the Russian-Ukrainian war have highlighted the importance of strengthening the resilience and autonomy of food systems.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Farmer and consumer empowerment in policy dialogues. There are significant investments in research, innovation and training in agroecology that are funded by the European Commission (in particular as well as other donors). The consumer demand for pesticide-free food is growing substantially in the capital city (Dakar).

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Diversity, Equity and inclusion of women, youth and smallholder farmers. They have created their own evaluation framework based on 15 major challenges that cover natural resources, family farming and sustainable agri-food systems. The initiative contributes to SDGs 2, 11, 12, 13, 15.

Etiquettable®

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Etiquettable / France
One or two key features: Digital app using consumer feedback and LCA-based scores
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Created by two innovators (a climate educator and a climate engineer) from different backgrounds in 2009, eCO2 received funding from the French ecological transition agency (ADEME) in 2017, to create the Etiquettable mobile application. As part of the work put into developing the app, eCO2 created a collective of sustainable consumption actors – Yuka, ScanUp, Open Food Facts, FrigoMagic, La Fourche, FoodChéri, marmiton and SeaZon – to develop Eco-score®. Eco-score® uses Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) [based on the Agribalyse® database] to give a score about the environmental sustainability of food

Which ambitions and objectives: Design and implement actions aimed at accelerating the ecological transition through changes in behaviour. In particular, they offer awareness-raising programmes aimed at local communities. Etiquettable aims to contribute to a more sustainable diet and seeks to bring together disparate information on cooking, the environment and nutrition. It therefore offers multi-functional services in one: a list of seasonal fruit and vegetables as well as nutrition information, endangered fish species, sustainable recipes to share and rate, geolocation of committed restaurants, sustainable cooking tips and various other information.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: eCO2 is social enterprise « Entreprise Solidaire d'Utilité Sociale » and Eco-score® is a collective of social enterprises. Eco-score® is a registered trademark protected by ADEME since 2020. Usage licenses have been granted to organizations performing ratings, on a temporary and transitional basis pending future regulations (Climate and Resilience Law 2021).

What external input and output: The app was user-driven in its design (users tested the app at different stages of development) and it includes recipes and tips from chefs committed to sustainable cooking. Underlying this app there is an impact and recipe sourcing calculation, which is based on the food databases of the French Food Safety and Environment authorities. A scientific committee works with the developers to conduct continuous food impact assessments and research on the impact of public information and communication about nutrition and environmental qualities of food. The application is interactive and allows all users to add new food, tips, recipes, restaurant reviews, etc. that builds the community trust.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
<p>The Grenelle de l'environnement (an open multi-party debate in 2007) introduced environmental labelling in 2009</p> <p>The EU Green Deal encourages eco-labelling</p>	<p>Environmental consultants</p> <p>Civil Society Organisations</p> <p>Ecological Transition Agency</p> <p>Private labels</p>	<p>Sustainability information , eco-scores, ethical restaurant labels, consumer ratings</p>	<p>A digital app that facilitates the access to this information</p> <p>Consumer feedback and rating of restaurants and vendors</p>	<p>Voluntary eco-labelling since 2013</p> <p>Circular Economy Road map 2018</p> <p>Article 15 of Law n° 2020-105 to protect against Waste and to promote the circular economy</p> <p>2023 Eco-labelling should be obligatory</p>	<p>Increased use of the app (>2%/year)</p> <p>Increased coverage (5892 producers & shops in 2023, >24% since 2021; 1263 restaurants, >26% since 2021)</p>	<p>2009 – eCO2 created</p> <p>2017 – Etiquettable launched</p> <p>2020 – Eco-score registered with ADEME</p> <p>2023 – Eco-score official ADEME eco-label</p>

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
eCO2 – knowledge about LCA	Flexible – Adapting the app to consumer feedback	Networked domestically	Yes – working on the Eco-Score in a collective	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Place to Bio – geolocalisation of organic and responsible restaurants	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – organic and responsible restaurants	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Bon pour le climat – lists eco-calculated recipes	Flexible – adapts their information based on Etiquettable	Networked domestically	Yes – sustainable ingredients	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
CartoVrac – references bulk goods stores from OpenStreetMap	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – sustainable ingredients	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Ecotable and FIG – certify (maintain lists of) restaurants according to a standard for eco-responsibility	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – responsible restaurants	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Vegoresto – maintains a list of vegan or vegan-friendly restaurants	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – vegan restaurants	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Ethic Ocean – synthesizes knowledge about seafood	Inflexible – simply providing information	Networked domestically	Yes – protection of marine biodiversity	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets
Government Agency (ADEME) – legitimizes and finances the innovation	Flexible - is mediating between government and the social actors	Networked domestically	Yes – to guide the ecological transition	Yes – healthy and sustainable diets

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

All of the private actors are mission-driven social enterprises or NGOs. Their individual and collective missions are to participate in changing how food is produced and consumed. ADEME is making significant investments so to implement mandatory eco-labelling.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The unsustainability of current diets – particularly related to food waste, biodiversity loss and low levels of consumption of (in season) vegetables.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

With the Etiquettable app, and with the accompanying Eco-score® and ratings on restaurants and sales points, consumers are better informed about where they can eat more sustainably. Consumers are also engaged by contributing to the online maps and reporting those restaurants and sales points that are not delivering on their sustainability promise.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Reduction of food waste, sustainable packaging, biodiversity, transparency and origin of ingredients, seasonality of ingredients, certified production, product environmental footprint (LCA). The initiative contributes to SDGs 2, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country

Climate Smart Chefs

One or two key features:

promotion of low emission, nutritious and affordable diets

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

Running (01/01/2022 – 31/12/2024)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:

The LIFE CLIMATE SMART CHEFS is a European project receiving funding from the LIFE Programme of the European Union. It aims to contribute to the development and implementation of the EU Climate Policy and the Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy. Project partners are one philanthropic funder, world's leading educational and training centre for the Italian food and beverage and hospitality sectors, the largest networks of Vocational Education and Training providers in Italy, a university, menu management software company.

Which ambitions and objectives:

The main project objectives are:

- To increase the awareness on the relationship between food and climate change at the EU level.
- To engage chefs as active changemakers and promoters of low emission, nutritious and affordable diets in the EU.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Thanks to the project's activities a Network of Life Climate Smart Chefs has been created made of chef associations, restaurants, hotels and caterers who will engage in the fight against food waste, reducing carbon emissions and water consumption: [The network - Life Climate Smart Chefs](#)

What external input and output:

- the implementation of a high-level training course for chefs
- the development of a digital tool to design climate smart menus
- the creation of an Award dedicated to climate smart chefs and local initiatives promoting sustainable diets
- the creation of an EU Network of chef associations
- the implementation of the Life Climate Smart Chefs Vision 2030, a strategic paper aimed at providing policy recommendations and supporting EU Climate Policy.

[Home - Life Climate Smart Chefs](#)

[CSC-brochure-ENG-02 \(climatesmartchefs.eu\)](#)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food sustainability and healthy diets	Vocational training institutes in the hospitality sectors, universities, IT companies, chef associations, restaurants, hotels and caterers.	An high-level training course, digital tools, an award, a strategic paper.	Creating a stable network of chefs working in restaurants and catering companies committed to food sustainability.	Make food businesses and their customers to make more informed and environmentally-conscious decision	Raising awareness among chefs on the importance of food sustainability and at the same time enhancing their skills and competencies in preparing healthy and sustainable menus.	Duration of the LIFE project: 01/01/2022 – 31/12/2024

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
<p>Chefs are provided a training on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Why food is important for our planet's future and for solving climate change. - How to reduce food waste and save money - How to communicate the value of sustainability with your staff, suppliers and customersow to use a specially designed menu engineering tool to create menus that are healthy, affordable and good for the planet. 	<p>The training activities provided through this project are open to any chef interested in the topic despite its affiliation to a company or association part of the network.</p>	<p>The partnership sees very diverse partners from the vocational training, IT and hospitality sector coming together and share expertise/ develop skills.</p>	<p>The main goal is to provide turn chefs in active promoters of sustainable diets and encourage them to communicate and disseminate science-based information.</p>	<p>The project was able to mobilise caterers and chefs associations in one year. The challenge will be to maintain this mobilisation beyond the end of the project.</p>

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision-making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Within this projects, chefs are identified as potential active changemakers and promoters of low emission, nutritious and affordable diets in the EU.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Unsustainable and unhealthy diets in the hospitality sector.
Food loss and waste in the hospitality sector.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

One of the action, beyond the ones mentioned above, is the he implementation of the Life Climate Smart Chefs Vision 2030, a strategic paper aimed at providing policy recommendations.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The project is promoting the 'Foodprint' too is a fully automated, easy-to-use environmental impact scoring, display, and emission reporting system for the hospitality and food service (HaFS) sector. The aim is to combines the latest research with cutting-edge technology to support chefs and organisations on their journey to carbon neutrality.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: SFS-MED Platform (Italy)

One or two key features: The SFS-MED Platform is a multi-stakeholder initiative aimed at promoting collaborative actions for the sustainable transformation of food systems in the Mediterranean, ultimately accelerating progress on the delivery of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development in the region.

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The founding members began circulating the idea with the OPN-SFSP in 2018, which culminated in the organization of the 2nd World Conference on the Revitalization of the Mediterranean Diet on “Strategies towards More Sustainable Food Systems in the Mediterranean Region. The Mediterranean Diet as a Lever Bridging Consumption and Production in a Sustainable and Healthy Way”, held in Palermo, in May 2019. A MOU was signed between CIHEAM, FAO and UfMS in January 2021 and two food system dialogues were held in preparation for the UNFSS and the 3rd World Conference on Sustainable Food Systems in the Mediterranean.

Which ambitions and objectives: The platform aims to be forum for dialogue and collaboration on priority themes for sustainable food systems in the Mediterranean, acting as a neutral facilitator of multi-stakeholder exchange to enhance policy coherence, build trust, and promote the effective implementation of actions.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Created in 2021 by the International Centre for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies (CIHEAM), the Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN (FAO), the Union for the Mediterranean (UfMS) and the Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA), it is a network for strengthening knowledge sharing and capacity building related to sustainable food consumption and production across the Mediterranean.

What external input and output: The platform aims to rebalance sustainability and finance. Dedicated support for the co-creation of flagship projects and investment proposals will enable actors in Mediterranean food systems to access funding and scale up sustainable investments. The platform catalyses regional cooperation for data sharing, science diplomacy, and the advancement of green and blue practices, as well as inclusive and digital innovation

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
The Mediterranean diet is threatened by climate change and changing food habits	Researchers, public policy-makers, funding agencies, NGOs, consumers organizations	Knowledge, investments, digital technologies	Co-creation of flagship projects, investment proposals, data sharing, scientific diplomacy	Forum for dialogue and collaboration on 5 themes (that will be revisited periodically)	3 webinars per year on priority topics, the bi-yearly conference on the Mediterranean Diet, Communities of Practice, Funding co-creation projects (tbd)	2019 – 2 nd World Conference on the Mediterranean Diet 2021 – MOU establishing the SFS-MED

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
CIHEAM – scientific knowledge production	Flexible – has adapted research to challenges of climate change	Clusters organized in a regional network	Yes, the 5 priorities of action were defined together	Yes, they are part of the OPN-SFSP and UNFSS Coalitions
FAO – international knowledge broker	Flexible – has included the EU Mediterranean region in its programme	Clusters organized in a regional network	Yes, the 5 priorities of action were defined together	Yes, they are part of the OPN-SFSP and UNFSS Coalitions
UfMS – governments of Member States	Flexible – new collaborations in the region	Clusters organized in a regional network	Yes, the 5 priorities of action were defined together	Yes, they are part of intergovernmental groups in EU and AU
PRIMA – funding mechanism for innovation	Flexible – opportunities for funding co-creation and innovation	Clusters organized in a regional network	Yes, the 5 priorities of action were defined together	Yes, they collaborate with EU research networks

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

With the creation of this new regional platform, the actors have changed the way in which they make decisions about the funding of investments for SFS. The collaboration among State governments, research and innovation donors and the research institutes offers an interesting example for the EU Partnership for SFS.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

There are four pillars of unsustainable circumstances in the food system that the platform presented in this case is addressing. In terms of environmental unsustainability, the Mediterranean region is suffering from over fishing, insufficient water resources, and unsustainable sources of energy. The current rates of unemployment and economic inequalities between northern and southern Mediterranean countries are unsustainable. Migration in the Mediterranean basin and gender inequalities exacerbate unsustainable lifestyles. Finally, urbanization and the nutrition transition are threatening the Mediterranean diet – which is largely based on legumes, vegetables, fruits and whole grains.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Knowledge creation, sharing and new collaborations are emerging within this platform. The platform is preparing to support investment projects in sustainable blue and green economies, as well as in efforts to support the production and consumption of food products that are foundations of the Mediterranean diet.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Diversity, inclusion and equity are key aspects of the food systems that are being promoted. Specifically, the platform is measuring its contributions to SDG 2, 12 (12.1, 12.2, 12.3, 12.8), 17.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country ...The Sustainable Food Systems Program (SPNF-PKKY) Himachal Pradesh / India
One or two key features: ...Training programme for producers to adopt natural farming, evaluation and certification system for local and public markets
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running.....

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Development of **Framework for Sustainable Food System Platform for Natural Farming (SuSPNF)**, which is an innovative self-assessment farmers' certification methodology. Based on an innovative fellowship between the state government of Himachal Pradesh and the Farmers and Producers Organizations of natural farmers. Inspired by Subhash Palekar Father of Natural Farming Method.

Which ambitions and objectives: Captive outlets for target selling of natural farming produce; Canopies and other local promotion means for natural farming farmers; Logos and Branding of the natural produce of the state.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The project was originally all run out of the State government's Agriculture office's State Project Implementation unit (SPIU). In 2022, a boutique was opened to sell certified products in the State capital city. Since 2023, partnership forged with the Dr. YS Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry to develop training on natural farming and sustainable food systems.

What external input and output: Knowledge sharing with Zero Budget Natural Farming in Andhra Pradesh, FAO-INRAE handbook for innovators on sustainable food systems and e-learning course. PGSOC, a private, national level organic participatory guarantee system. IFOAM Organics International

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
State level programme to transition all farmers in the state to natural farming	State government, Natural farmers, University, Farm advisors, Public shop	Apples, horticulture crops, wild collected crops, processed products	Adoption of Natural farming practices 3 * Certification scheme	Bilingual Default Access for new farmers (1*) Fast in response with a set time frame Perpetual Status for farmers (unless system-triggered) Peer Review Public Domain - Checks and Balances	Inclusion of most farmers in the State. Notable reduction in synthetic inputs Reduction in the costs of farming	Officially launched in 2018 No end date in sight

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
State government – financial incentives and label	Flexible - has accepted innovative forms of certification	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	With other States and federal government
Natural farmers – farming practices, peer reviews	Flexible – has changed farming practice	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	With other farmers to form peer groups
University – training	Flexible - has developed new curricula	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	With national and international researchers
Computer scientists - digital platform, transparency	Flexible – adapting platform to fit needs	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	No
Public shop – market access	Flexible – adapting to public and private market quality criteria	Networked with other actors	Natural farming	No

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

This initiative emerged from dialogues that had been going on in the State for many years about the need to reduce pesticides use in order to improve the health of farmers. The government collaborated with the University, consultants, external researchers and computer scientists in order to study and then develop a certification system that would meet the needs of the farmers and ensure that the products could be sold and consumed within the state and external to the state. They have been seeking

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The first element is an unsustainable use of pesticides in agriculture and the health and food safety concerns that accompany it. The second element is the unsustainable cost of industrial farming. Third, the case addresses the unsustainable export of produce outside of the state and encourages the consumption of diversified production within the state.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

The first action is training of farmers in natural farming practices through the public extension system. The second is the development of an evaluation and certification system that enables farmers to progress from their point of entry at 1* to full achievement of natural farming at 3*. 2* and 3* farmers can use the SPNF seal. 3* farmers have access to the official marketing channels of the program and additional state incentives.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The core indicators are related to the use of off-farm sourced inputs. A mapping against the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has been completed and the SPNF-HP program has been found to contribute to 7 of the 17 SDGs (addressing 15 targets and 18 indicators). Specifically: 1 (1.4), 2 (2.3, 2.4, 2.5), 6 (6.4), 8 (8.3, 8.9), 9 (9.3), 12 (12.1, 12.3, 12.6, 12.7) and 15 (15.3, 15.4, 15.9)

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Tanzania Organic Agriculture Movement (TOAM) / Tanzania
One or two key features: National multi-stakeholder platform that represents the Organic sector and governs the use of the East African Organic Products Standards in Tanzania
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Tanzania Organic Agriculture Movement (TOAM) is a registered NGO formed in 2005 under the NGO Act of 2002. They are an umbrella organization that coordinates and promotes the development of organic farming among farmers, distributors and consumers through networking and information distribution.

Which ambitions and objectives: TOAM sees development of the organic farming sector as a crucial factor for sustainable livelihoods and envisions establishing a vibrant, sustainable and mutually beneficial organic sector in Tanzania.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: TOAM has a secretariat with >10 full time employees and is governed by a Board of Directors, led by a Chairperson. They are a member-based organization and count 115 members. These members include various types of institutions and organizations such as farmers associations and cooperatives, NGOs, organic operators, companies, distributors, researchers and trainers.

What external input and output: TOAM exists to provide capacity building on organic practices, quality management for compliance to organic standards, improvement to value chains, lobbying and advocating for supportive policies, and information collection and distribution. TOAM provides and distributes information on organic food to its members and other stakeholders in the whole of Tanzania.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Organic sector focused almost exclusively on export and a domestic agriculture policy focused on green revolution technologies. Yet a growing domestic consumer interest in sustainability	Farmers Orgs, national NGOs, Certifiers, Donors, Sokoine University, Participatory Guarantee Systems (PGS) Ministries of Agriculture and Trade	Tropical fruits, seasonal vegetables, Spices, coffee, cosmetics, knowledge	Farmer training, Creation of PGS, National accreditation for the Kilimo Hai label, Policy advocacy, Consumer awareness and rural radio	Regional standard for organic agriculture Third-party and PGS certification authorized New Training Centre of Excellence, with an Organic programme planned	4 th largest number of Organic certified farms in the World Organic agriculture strategy finalised in 2023	2005: Creation of TOAM 2007: Creation of East African Kilimo Hai Mark 2017: One stop shop for TZ organic created 2023: Organic Sector strategy

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
TOAM – knowledge about organic certification	Flexible – TOAM adapts to the ministry and its members	Networked domestically and on the continent	Yes – common mission and values for the organization	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
TOAM Board – political alliances and legitimacy	Flexible – adapts to the ministry and TOAM members	Networked on the continent	Yes – common mission and values for the organization	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
Farmer members – knowledge about organic agriculture	Flexible – adapts to climate and market pressures	Clusters through farmer groups and PGS	Sometimes – not all farmers have the same goal	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
Ministry of Agriculture – political will	Semi-flexible – adapts to TOAM advocacy, but dependent on government policy	Networked with TOAM and Donors	Sometimes – the government seeks to reduce food insecurity and adapt to climate-change	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
NGO members – complementary projects, knowledge	Semi-flexible – combines interest for some common advocacy, but competes for donor funding	Networked within TOAM	Sometimes – not all NGOs share the same mission and have different visions of sustainability	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally
Donors - funding	Inflexible – Donor funding is tied to donor priorities	Usually 1-1 interactions	No – each donor has its own goal in line with its national/organizational strategy (not always organic)	Yes – expansion of organic production and consumption nationally

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

All of the actors in this case recognize that they have a role to play in the sustainability transition of their food system. While there is not full government support for organic agriculture in the country, the recent policy advances recognizes the importance of organic in creating sustainable food systems in the country. TOAM is a forum of stakeholders in the organic sector. It creates platforms for larger and louder voices for influencing policy makers and practitioners on adoption of best practices in the organic sector. There are a handful of donors who are also committed to supporting the transition of local food systems towards sustainability.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

Capital intensive agriculture is not sustainable for the majority of smallholder farmers, who are increasingly being excluded from the food system. The increased use in pesticides has had negative effects on farmer worker health and chemical residues on food in the local markets are increasing. The dependence on export markets for organic products creates risks for the resilience of the domestic market, where demand is growing rapidly for healthy food.

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

TOAM is taking action on food, nutrition and health by increasing the awareness of food consumers on health benefits of organic foods. TOAM empowers smallholder farmers to take control of their seed security and take back control over their food systems by reclaiming their food sovereignty. TOAM promotes the relevance of Organic Agriculture on environmental management, climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation. TOAM fosters gender equitable access and benefits of organic value chains outcomes by empowering women and youth on decision making and control on organic farming systems and utilization. TOAM generates evidence on how, where and through which value chains, organic farming can offer alternative sustainable livelihoods strategies. TOAM takes custodianship of branding and certification ensuring visibility, recognition, and credibility of organic commodities in the market.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Diversity, Equity and inclusion of women, youth and smallholder farmers. They measure the number of certified farmers and the value of the domestic market. The initiative contributes to SDGs 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 10, 12, 15, 17.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Réseau Semences Paysannes, France

One or two key features:

Promotion of biodiversity

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:

Which ambitions and objectives: The association aims to bring together and network the actors of cultivated biodiversity to promote the dissemination of farmers' seeds and associated know-how, develop and promote their dynamic management in farms and gardens, as well as implement any other actions that can contribute to it.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The association has a board: [Organigramme RSP \(semencespaysannes.org\)](http://semencespaysannes.org). Members of the association are National farmers organisations, Producers associations, associations working on biodiversity preservation, artisanal seed growers, etc.

What external input and output: Wide awareness raising activities, ad hoc training, information sessions promotion of local initiatives.

Réseau Semences Paysannes - L'association

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Peasants' seeds as key element to maintain cultivated biodiversity essential to our food.	Peasants	Events, trainings, meetings, legal advice.		I.e. national reform of seeds at European level or GMO regulation.	For example: In 2021 more than 100 training were delivered. Annual 'organisation of 'Semain des Semences Paysannes', creation' Link	The network exists since 2003.

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
The group provides trainings and organise awareness raising activitnes (i.e. Semaine de semences paysannes). Legal advice is provided. Ad hoc thematic working groups on the different types of seeds have been established.		National farmers organisations, Producers associations, associations working on biodiversity preservation, artisanal seed growers.	Promotion and commercialisation of traditional seeds.	Lawyers.

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The association is actively promoting through its activities social and ecological agriculture rooted in the territories.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

The industry's radical monopoly on seeds has led to the disappearance of 75% of cultivated biodiversity in 50 years

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Safeguarding and dissemination of vegetable and fruit varieties and local cereals, but also grass species; Organization of national and international meetings, trips study to exchange seeds and know-how; Legal watch to decipher the evolutions of a context binding regulations and policies for farmers' seeds; Participatory selection projects to safeguard and select suitable population-varieties organic and peasant farming; Training to transmit and spread knowledge and know-how around cultivated biodiversity.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

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Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: Sustainable Food Places UK

One or two key features: brings together pioneering food partnerships across the UK that are driving innovation and best-practice in all aspects of healthy and sustainable food

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): running since 2020 (5-year Sustainable Food Places programme)

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Starting with a handful of places in 2010 with funding of the Esmée Fairbairn Foundation from 2013 – 2019 the organization grew up to 80 SFPs today and reaching out internationally to spread the concept

Which ambitions and objectives:

1. establish a cross-sector food partnership in the UK involving local authorities, public sector, business, academia, third sector
2. Develop shared vision, strategy and action plan to enhance the importance of healthy and sustainable food
3. Working together to spread the vision beyond UK

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: Since 2010 helping Sustainable Food Places through knowledge sharing, strategizing, advise and support to enable local food partnerships to drive changes to local policy and practice, provide grants

What external input and output: Funding from the Esmée Fairbairn Foundation & National Lottery Community Fund, knowledge exchange with international networks (such as ICLEI, C40, MUFPF)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Local food supply chains	Policy makers, businesses, local civil society	Food partnerships on local levels	Support of local Food partnerships through: webinars, networking, toolkits etc.	Dependent on the activity and compliance of local food actors; cannot completely predict/influence actual outcomes	Network of sustainable food places has significantly grown in the last decade	Increased funding for their actions until 2026, generally since 2010

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Workshops, toolkits, coaching, networking	Adopting to needs of local food systems and including insights into work; not inclusive towards international supply chains	Actor consists of various organisations and members who are made up of business, farmers, civil society	Yes, joint goal is to have a radical shift in our food and farming system towards agroecological production, sustainable diets and an end to food waste	Works together with international city networks, such as ICLEI, C40, Eurocities

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Their goal is to inspire and support local food initiatives to succeed in changing local Food Systems. Their approach doesn't involve a proposed strategy but invites initiatives to think about their local system and what could be done to address its unsustainability

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

This varies with the local community they work with. Best-Practices from their work are: Aberdeen becoming a Sustainable Fish City, Micro grant to 27 small businesses and food initiatives to adapt to covid (Belfast), Vertical Farming within Old Mills (Bradford), Halal Lamb Farm-to-Fork Feasibility (identifying key elements of local lamb supply chain (Bradford) and many more, to find [here](#).

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Empowering and encouraging the actors that know their food system best: civil society, local business and farmers to address the topic that is most urgent in the local context. The Toolkit provides guides and workshops on mapping food systems or approaching policymakers, ways of communications and funding opportunities.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Social, economic and environmental sustainability go hand in hand. What indicators are weighted most is up to the specific local community.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country: 4 per 1000 initiative / International, The Executive Secretariat is hosted by The Alliance Bioversity International-CIAT, (France).

One or two key features: The International "4 per 1000" initiative encourages stakeholders to engage in a transition towards a regenerative, productive, highly resilient agriculture, based on appropriate land and soil management, which creates jobs and income and thus leads to sustainable development.

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Farmers, economic players, local authorities and States then joined forces with researchers around the initiative, recorded on the solutions agenda (Lima-Paris Agenda for Action) during this same COP.

Which ambitions and objectives: 24 objectives under 6 goals in the strategic plan

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: 744 members and partners, 104 countries of origin, 67 producer organizations

What external input and output: CO₂ into the soil, output is the reduced emissions.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Soil	Agriculture, i.e. farmers	Healthy soils	Primary food production in fields	30-40 cm layer of soil in agricultural or forestry use	Reduction of carbon from the atmosphere	20-30 years
	Forestry, i.e. forest owners, governments	Food from fields				

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Enhancing biological processes for carbon capture to increase the levels of soil carbon	Concentrating activities in soils creates flexibility as the places for activities can be found nearly everywhere	Collaboration between stakeholders of the "Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU)"	Accelerating climate change mitigation	Vision: Worldwide healthy and carbon-rich soils to combat climate change and end hunger.
			Intensifying the adaptation of agriculture to climate change	
			Improve food security	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The activities of the initiative will significantly increase the sustainability of the food system.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address? Carbon emissions in the atmosphere, reduced soil health

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System? Improving soil health via regenerative practices in agriculture and forestry

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use? The Strategic plan includes six goals, the baseline and targets for 2030 and 2050, enabling the monitoring of the initiative

Name of the food systems co-creation case / CountryBiocode / Finland.....
 One or two key features: The company provides tools for calculating CO²-emissions for food system actors.....
 Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running.....

Photo banner (including country)

bio<code

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The company was founded by the Association of ProAgria Centres' and Mtech Digital Solutions', who sought solutions to decarbonise food production.

Which ambitions and objectives: Decarbonising food production

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The company started as providing CO²-emission calculating services, and has evolved into other innovations within the field of sustainable food system

What external input and output: Input: information from the companies who buy the services, output: Carbon footprinting

An illustration (Product, service, organisation change,

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Carbon emissions	Farms	Information on carbon footprint of the product	Finding information on emissions of the raw materials	Information available limits the calculations	Information on the carbon footprint of a specific product	Not specified
	Food processing companies	CO ² footprint labels				
	Grocery stores					
	Information processing company					

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Quantitative information on emissions	The actor is building new products and providing innovations as well as growing the customer base on the first product	Cooperation with customers, but also other SFS actors such as developer organisations and the founding NGO	Reduction of CO ² -emissions of the food products	Reduction of emissions

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Actively developing and offering new products supporting the sustainability activities of food system actors.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address? Calculation of carbon emissions of food products, though food system – from field to fork, including processing and retail

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System? Calculating the emissions and thereby providing the opportunity to efficiently reduce emissions and verify the process.

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Carbon footprint

Influences SDGs 12 responsible consumption and production, 13 climate action, 17 partnership for the goals

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country

REKO, Regional Networks for Fair Consumption, 500 groups in FINLAND and the Nordic Countries.....

One or two key features:

From Producer to Consumer, without middlemen. Informal network of producers and customers.....

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

Running.....

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:

The farmers and consumers have created the practice together in order to shorten the food chain and support local food producers.....

Which ambitions and objectives: The objectives are to provide a distribution model offering customers an opportunity to order products directly from the producer, without the need for middlemen.....

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The groups are run by volunteers, and with a very low level of organisation or bureaucracy.....

What external input and output: The collection point is provided by a local supermarket, and the platform for the network by Meta / Facebook.....

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Distribution network: Each region has two FB-groups: One for producers (instructing, information-sharing), and one for public (for making orders).	Producers and consumers	Local food products	Distribution at a specifically agreed location directly from producer to consumer	Rules for the producers are provided in a regional producer Facebook group	Short food chains	Varies, distribution for example once every second week
				Pre-approved customers, rules in the FB-group	Fresh products	
					Low rate of production	

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Informal organization level	Adapts according to customer needs	Informal network in Facebook	Local food	Some informal cooperation within the REKO network
Low level of bureaucracy	Short distribution chains	Two-way interaction between producers and consumers	Minimally processed, safe food	Actors in the networks are generally interested in fair and sustainable food system, and enhance the objectives through various other channels
Easy access for farmers			Fair and just trade for everyone	
Large variety of product groups represented				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors (e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Short production and distribution chains generate less emissions. Local food markets support the social sustainability within the community. Actors in the networks are generally interested in fair and sustainable food system, and enhance the objectives through various other channels.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?Long production chains, use of non-fresh food products, non-just distribution system, long travel distances of food products.....

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?Organizing an informal network of producers and customers, who can agree on the orders via Facebook group.....

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The number of local REKO distribution networks.

Influences SDGs 1 no poverty, 2 zero hunger, 3 good health and well-being, 5 gender equality, 8 decent work and economic growth, 10 reduced inequalities, 11 sustainable cities and communities, 12 responsible consumption and production, 17 partnerships for the goals.....

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country ...ResQ Club / Finland.....
One or two key features: ...An application connecting restaurants, cafes and grocery stores to customers who want to reduce food waste in an affordable manner.....
Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): ...Running.....

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: ...Brings food waste products to one easily accessible platform.....

Which ambitions and objectives:Reaching zero food waste.....

Evolution of their governance model and organisation:Private company...

What external input and output:Food waste problem, growth of the use of mobile applications.....

An illustration
 (Product, service,
 organisation change, ...)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Restaurants, cafes, grocery stores	People who work at the restaurants, cafes and grocery stores	Waste quality meals, snacks, groceries	ResQ application	Use of cellphone and a mobile app with the use of a payment method are required	Less food waste	0-4 hours from the food provider to the customer depending on the customer
	Customers			Waste food		

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Answering to the needs of food providers and customers	The service is offered to various food providers and is therefore very flexible	Actors are supported by campaigns and materials	Reduction of food waste from food providers	Working in cooperation with restaurants and other food service providers.
Connecting the support for sustainability to affordable pricing				

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

Functions in 124 / 309 municipalities in Finland.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?Food waste.....

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

.....Support for food service providers and grocery stores to use food waste.....

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The number of meals rescued and the reduced amounts of wasted food.

Influences SDG 12, responsible production and consumption, 13 Climate Action

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country Vegan challenge / Finland

One or two key features: Challenges the participant to try vegan diet for one month for the climate in a positive way

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: 10 years of cooperation with public figures and influencers as well as ordinary consumers / food citizens. Long history of supporting vegan diets

Which ambitions and objectives: 8 reasons for motivation
Aiming at making vegan diet easy and fun, and for various kinds of consumers

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: NGO Oikeutta eläimille (justice for animals) is the operating organisation of Vegan Challenge. Over time, the challenge has transformed into a challenge aimed at regular consumers, not only for animal rights activists

What external input and output: Input: Challenging people to try vegan diet for one month by providing various ways of support: mentors, social media groups, recipes... output: More people on vegan or partly vegan diet.

An illustration
 (Product, service, organisation change, ...)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Vegan diet	NGO actors	Vegan food	Buying	Vegan diet to be followed	Vegan or semi-vegan diets	One month
	Public figures	Community	Preparing	Various incentives for action		
	Food citizens	Recipes				
	Food producers					
	Grocery Stores					

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
Transforming activism into an easily accessible form	Adapting into including varying motivations to try vegan diets	High level of interaction between actors on social media and via newsletter	Support for vegan diet	Works together with various clusters: Common goal is to support vegan diet.

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

The motivation for sustainability actions for participants vary from : environment, climate, water, health, animal production, not missing out, delicacies, peer support.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address? Animal production (with its various unwished effects for climate).

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System? Supporting vegan diet in a positive manner by not making consumers feel guilty of their choices but by encouraging the small steps to change in various ways

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

Annual number of participants to the challenge

Influences SDGs 6 clean water and sanitation, 12 responsible consumption and production, 13 climate action, 14 life below water, 15 life on land, 17 partnership for the goals

Name of the food systems co-creation case / CountryA New York City Framework for Good Food Purchasing / USA
 One or two key features: ...it try to answer an urgent problem that characterizes several context about the flow of communication between different realms/contexts and area.....
 Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped): Running.....

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: Which ambitions and objectives: The program seeks to improve the food the City serves to most vulnerable populations, including school children, older adults, people in homeless shelters or held in our prisons. Implementing GFP allows the city to measure and improve performance across the different areas

Evolution of their governance model and organisation: The City of New York spends nearly half a billion dollars on food each year to serve more than 230 million meals to our City's most vulnerable populations. The program has been developed to establishes a transparent, clear foundation for tracking food purchases and monitoring performance annually with clear data tied to metrics: nutrition, local economies, a valued workforce, environmental sustainability, and animal welfare

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food aids	farmers	Food aids		There are several legal restrictions that this programme is trying to overcome	Monitoring framework	
monitoring	Officers, municipalities					

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
	Different actors are put together to collect information and systematize the food system and logistics. In this sense all are forced to adapt to each other and share information adaptation	Share information	The municipality define a common aim	

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision-making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

This framework, developed by The Center for Good Food Purchasing, who is partnered with The City of New York on this effort, is a values-based procurement framework that helps institutions better understand the source of the food they purchase, and provides a methodology to quantify the impact of that food along five core values: nutrition, local economies, valued workforce, environmental sustainability, and animal welfare.

As a collaborative citywide initiative managed by the Mayor's Office of Food Policy, NYC has developed its own approach to integrate the GFP principles, ensuring that money spent on food serves both the people and the planet.

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

In order to save food and meliorate the diet of poor people it is important to understand the availabilities, what there is in excess and what are the missing products, where are the most frequent food lost located in the system etc. This programme, which requires a collection of information requires also to align and create contact between actors that are not traditionally used to communicate. In that sense it is innovative and extremely urgent

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

Frequently the lack of information represents one of the greatest problem we have. This programme is answering this problem

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

This framework is meant to develop these indicators on food purchased and food waste

Name of the food systems co-creation case / CountryRefugees in the food system of a medium-sized city/ POLAND
 One or two key features:Answer to unexpected Crisis.....
 Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

Milan Pact Awards 2022		WROCLAW	
Country	Poland		
Population	642,700		
Title of policy or practice	Refugees in the food system of a medium-sized city		
Subtitle (optional)	The power of social capital as a key factor of responding to a food security threat in the context of the influx of refugees from Ukraine		
URL video	https://drive.google.com/drive/u/3/folders/12hP4y3Gpn-DoMowEZzdvvPpza9deYPP8		

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors: The refugee crisis has not only accentuated the need to have a local food policy but has also made people aware of the importance of social capital in grassroots activities responding to the crisis.

Which ambitions and objectives:

The described practice contributed to the spontaneous creation of a specific and efficient network of connections, inter alia, in the scope of securing access to food for the refugees, which is of our interest here. It was possible thanks to strong social capital, supported and built for many years. In fact, the food system, in which we were not interested until the signing of the Milan Pact, has successfully passed the test of "being sufficient" for everyone.

Evolution of their governance model and organisation:

The situation we experienced has contributed to mapping this network, to identifying its strengths and weaknesses, which in the future will result in its efficient and effective extension to include other entities and areas

What external input and output The economic impact means more than €2,000,000 of unplanned expenditure in the city. The refugee crisis has not only accentuated the need to have a local food policy but has also made people aware of the importance of social capital in grassroots activities responding to the crisis.

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)
Food aids	Governmental and non gov organizations, donors, food banks, gastronomic schools	Food aids	Coordination action to support refugees from Ukraine	It is an answer developed to a crisis and in that sense allowed to overcome traditional boundaries limiting actors collaboration and bureaucratic boundaries	Thanks to this, it was possible to immediately launch three large food distribution points in the city, run by the city and non-governmental organizations. In three months, more than 1.3 million meals were served in these places only. In addition to employees, nearly 2 thousand volunteers were permanently involved. The food was purchased by the self-government, received from donors, food banks and was prepared by gastronomic schools belonging to the self-government (more than 80 thousand meals).	February March and April 2022

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)
flexibility	All the actors are adapting to the situation of crisis	All actors interacted between each others	Yes	Each cluster work with other outside network locally or internationally

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors

(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

According to the data of the Union of Polish Metropolises, more than 3 million refugees from Ukraine came to Poland, of which more than 187 thousand chose Wrocław (in this number, over 42 thousand are children). In April 2022 23% of the city residents are Ukrainians, with the majority still needing care and support

What unsustainable circumstances in the Food System does this case address?

In connection with the described practice, we define the following challenges: ● Maintaining contact with persons/companies/networks of residents willing to act/local social innovators. ● Mapping the centers of the network of connections, created intentionally and automatically, with regard to the channels of food flow to, from and through the city as the origin of the food system diagnosis in the city

What actions are being taken to overcome unsustainable circumstances in the Food System?

the stimulation of enormous social capital, which – properly targeted – allowed to control the situation without paralyzing the city, while ensuring food security and protecting the dignity and autonomy of the refugees

What indicators for a Sustainable Food System does the case use?

The social impact is the coordination of grassroots food transfers with the contribution and measures of the city, which prevented the food exclusion of thousands of refugees, mainly women and children

6.3 Interview Guide

Funded by
the European Union

Interview guide

WP7 – Task 7.2

Version 1. March 2023

Funded by
the European Union

Background (for internal use)

Concept Note

Liaising with global organizations and their local partners will identify key opportunities, challenges, and priorities related to co-benefits and trade-offs toward SSFS at local, national, EU-wide, and global scales.

Interview process:

Conduct the interviews through video conferencing software such as ZOOM or MS Teams, record the video and store it on the FoodPathS sharepoint, along with this completed guide with notes in English [HERE](#).

Title the documents: *Interview_ORGANISATION INTERVIEWED_PARTNER NAME*

Objective of the interviews

- To bilaterally engage and learn from existing initiatives (e.g. Policy & City Labs, social innovation trajectories) and global organisations (FAO, WFP, WHO, UNICEF, UN Nutrition, etc.), national and sub national governments
- To identify best governance and implementation practices
- To identify “SSFS deals” at global, national and subnational level
- To identify potential mirror group participants
- Document lessons learned from best practices documented and serving as input for the Hub of FS Labs (WP4), policy advice (T6.2) and Prototype (D4, M18,WP2).

Email template

Dear XXX

PERSONAL introduction. Because of your connection with XXX, we would like to request 45 minutes of your time for an interview. We want to include the ideas, opinions, and experiences of people and organisations like yours in the development of the future Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems.

Are you available on XXX....

More about the partnership:

2

The Coordination and Support Action (CSA) FOODPathS, which is being executed by a consortium of 17 organisations under the coordination of INRAE, aims to prepare the ground for the future Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems (SFS).

This Partnership (with an estimated co-funding by the European Commission of ~175 Mio Euro) will play a crucial role in reaching the sustainability ambitions stated in the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and its overarching Green Deal. It will unite many different actors to jointly make the transition towards SFS a success.

More concretely, the CSA FOODPathS is building the prototype of the future Partnership, including the co-design of a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda – SRIA, a governance model, modus operandi, research-innovation-policy-education and training programs.

Background information about FoodPathS to share with interviewee

*share the following information as appropriate via the invitation to the interview, as an introduction during the interview or throughout the interview in conversation.

Overview of FoodPaths:

Current discussions and perspectives regarding the characteristics and priorities of a sustainable food system are plentiful, both globally and at a European level. Providing nutritious food while reducing negative environmental impact and ensuring food security has become a crucial challenge for our future. Interactions between all actors are necessary to address these challenges, overcoming the barriers that may arise due to their different perspectives and interests.

FOODPathS is a project funded by the European Commission that aims to offer a concrete pathway and necessary tools to support the establishment of the European Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems for People, Planet & Climate, to be launched in 2024 based on the experience gained during the project's lifetime. To ensure all voices are heard, the project engages actors from across the food system to create the framework in which the Partnership will operate.

The Consortium is working to co-create:

The **Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)** for the future SFS Partnership, inspiring diverse actors to respond to future calls for funding and innovative projects.

The **concepts for co-creation and definitions** that allow FS actors to share a common language and fruitfully work together.

A **Hub of Food Systems Living Labs** to overcome current fragmentation and show exemplary SFS cases in an accessible and interactive way.

A **Food System Observatory** for monitoring the sustainability performance of food systems

Education and training programs through a network of higher education institutes working in food systems that train the experts of the future and serve as sustainable playing grounds for emerging new ideas.

Future funding mechanisms and strategies that can maximise the impact of Research and Innovation towards SFS by gathering experiences and expertise of a Network of Funders.

Mirror Group description

October, 2022

FoodPathS will work with mirror groups in Europe and beyond to ensure that the SSFS Partnership is inclusive of farm to fork voices. We want to work with mirror groups in order to

- hear the priorities, reflections, and feedback of groups impacted by the establishment of a SSFS partnership
- build an inclusive, transparent, partnership
- learn about best governance and implementation practices
- elevate the voices and stories of mirror group participants

Participants in the mirror groups will be local, regional, and national representatives including public sector, civil society and farmer organisations.

In practical terms, the FoodPaths consortium will:

- Engage with five mirror groups within Europe (5-10 organisations)
- Engage with five mirror groups outside of Europe (5-10 organisations)
- organize a short series of exchange events for mirror group participants and they will also be invited to join the FoodPathS annual event.
 - One event for mirror groups within Europe
 - One event for mirror groups outside of Europe
 - One for both
- The mirror groups will include representation from southern, northern, eastern, western, and central Europe, as well as South America, North America, Africa, Australia, and Asia.

Result will be inclusion of F2F voices and their ideas by writing in the development and communication of the SSFS Partnership and RIPE concept, as well as, Toolkit for avoiding local and global trade-offs in a sustainable food system, likely a collection of case studies and guidance materials, such as factsheets and good practices for actions, classified at the local, national, EU-wide, and global scales.

Why we want to speak with your organisation:

To be personalized by the interviewer before the interview

Interviewee information

Name:

Title:

Organisation:

Contact information:

4

Questions to ask

1. Please, tell me a bit about your XXXX (deal, initiative, best practice) and how it came to be where it is today...
2. What is your legal and governance structure?
3. How do you address polarisation and challenges related to differing opinions about sustainability and food system transformation?
4. What are your core activities related to food system work?

<u>Who are your core partners?</u>	<u>Primary target audience/clients?</u>

5. What challenges/issues related to sustainability do you seek to address and how?
 - Challenges/issues:
 - Actions to overcome them:
6. What indicators for sustainability do you work with?
7. What do you think needs to be done practically in order to transition to a sustainable food system?
 - Are there risks involved?
 - What are the trade-offs?
 - What are the potential benefits?

(if asked for clarification....E.g. gentrification related to urban agriculture or rising costs of food or corporate influence etc.)

8. Can you share an example (or 3 ;-)) of effective food related policy? (on local, national, or regional scale) What made it successful?

9. What 3 things are most important for FOODPathS to consider while establishing the framework for a European partnership for sustainable food systems?

10. Based on what you know and your experience, which key stakeholder groups / stakeholders are important to include in the development of the Food System Partnership?
 - What role should each of them have in the governance of this partnership?

11. Would you be interested in being considered for participating in a mirror group?

12. What other organisations should we talk with and/or consider for mirror groups?
 - Outside Europe
 - Within Europe

13. Would you be willing/interested in being interviewed for a podcast?

Other:

6.4 Interviews

Interviewee Position	Organisation
Officer Sustainable Food Systems & Global City Food Co-Lead	ICLEI Europe
EU Projects Manager	Safe Food Advocacy
Program Manager	Biovision Foundation
Sustainable Food Systems Expert	UNEP
General Secretary	URGENCI
Project Officer	Terre de Liens
Project Manager	Agrifood Capital
CEO	Böna Factory
Chief Agroenvironmental Production Department	Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock
Food Policy Officer	Fair Local Green Deal Gent
Co-Founder	Ernährungsräte Netzwerk (Food Policy Council Network)
Programme Lead, Food Systems Governance Programme	GAIN
Several	Lithon Holdings, Blue Sky Impact
Food Programme Specialist	Namib Mills
Postdoctoral Reseracher	Aalto University
Food Smart Cities Coordinator	Rikolto
Senior Programme Officer	RUAF
Professor for Public Health	University of Helsinki
Several	Via Campesina Europe
Program Manager	World Food Forum
Co-Founder	Milan Urban Food Policy Pact
Director	IPES Food
Researcher	Athena
Senior Advisor	EAT Lancet
Program Manager	UN Nutritioun

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